

Sensing a solution to the packed problem

Can smart packaging help reduce the environmental impact of food waste?

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I will make my acknowledgment to this thesis in Swedish, as it is my first and most natural language. I can ensure any non-Swedish speaking reader that this dedication is filled of love and devotion to all of those who have helped me in the making of this thesis.

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Abstract

Globally, about a third of the food produced is wasted. To address this issue, the United Nations has set a sustainability goal of reducing food waste in retail and household by 50% to 2030. One factor that can be connected to the generation of food waste is packaging. When applied correctly, packaging prevents waste by providing protection and shelf life, but when packaging does not meet consumer needs, it can lead to waste. Designing better packaging is therefore a potential solution to reduce food waste. Recently, so-called “Smart packaging” innovation has been developed to meet that goal, which adds functions beyond protection, such as detecting spoilage.

This thesis investigates the potential of smart packaging innovation to decrease food waste, focused on a gas sensor that can detect bacterial growth in a packaging for fresh chicken. The sensor, placed on the inside of the package, changes color when spoilage reaches a critical level. The aim was to explore what potential smart packaging has in reducing food waste, and the total environmental impact. The study used two research approaches: A Life Cycle Analysis (LCA), which assesses the environmental impact of the smart packaging under different waste scenarios. The second approach investigated barriers and potentials for real-world implementation, through interviews with experts in the Swedish retailing sector.

The results indicate that, with a 50% reduction in waste, there is potentially a 5% decrease in environmental impact for 11 of 15 impact categories, including climate change. The barriers for introduction include regulatory issues, such as prohibition against selling chicken products after the use-by date, and concerns about the recyclability of the packaging. The research suggests that beef, which can be sold after its best-before date, may be a better candidate for the introduction of smart packaging, as it also has a higher environmental impact. Lastly, further studies are needed to explore consumer trust in the technology, which is crucial for the success of smart packaging innovations.

Key words: Food waste, Food waste reduction, packaging, smart packaging, gas sensor, retail.

Abstract

En tredjedel av maten vi produceras slängs, mat som har tagit resurser och landyta i anspråk för att bli till. För att få bukt med det globala matsvinnet har FN satt ett hållbarhetsmål att halvera matsvinnet inom mathandel och hushåll till 2030. En faktor som kan kopplas till matsvinn är förpackningar. När de används korrekt förhindrar förpackningar matsvinn genom att ge skydd och ökad hållbarhet, men när förpackningen inte möter konsumentens behov kan det leda till onödigt matsvinn. Att designa bättre förpackningar, specifikt "smarta förpackningar", är därför en möjlig lösning på matsvinnproblematiken. En smart förpackningsinnovation innehåller fler funktioner än bara traditionellt skydd, såsom att förmågan att signalera när maten har blivit dålig.

I det här examensarbetet undersöktes vilken potential smart förpackningsinnovation har för att minska matsvinn, och den totala miljöpåverkan från den förpackade maten. En fallstudie fokuserad på en innovativ gassensor designad för förpackning av färsk kyckling genomfördes. Sensorn placeras på insidan av förpackningen och ändrar färg när bakterietillväxten nått en kritisk nivå. Fallstudien använde två forskningsmetoder: dels en livscykelanalys (LCA), som utvärderade miljöpåverkan av den förpackade maten under olika svinnscenarier. Den andra metoden undersökte hinder och potential för innovationens möte med dagligvaruhandeln, genom intervjuer med experter från tre svenska matkedjor.

Resultaten indikerar att vid en halvering av matsvinnet skulle en minskning av miljöpåverkan på cirka 5% kunna vara möjlig för 11 av 15 miljöpåverkanskategorierna som undersöktes. De hindren som identifierades genom expertintervjuerna pekade på att det kan vara svårt att introducera sensorn för just kycklingprodukter, eftersom det finns ett lagkrav på att märka färska kycklingprodukter med sista-förbrukningsdatum, efter vilket det inte är tillåtet att sälja produkten. Dessutom kan sensorn eventuellt göra förpackningen mindre återvinningsbar. Ett bättre alternativ skulle kunna vara att introducera sensorn på en köttprodukt, då dessa kan säljas med bäst-före datum som tillåter försäljning efter utgångsdatumet är passerat. Kött har dessutom en högre miljöpåverkan, och utgör ett större ekonomiskt svinn för handlarna. Slutligen underströks vikten av att etablera tillit hos konsumenterna som en centralt fråga för att innovationen ska lyckas uppfylla sitt syfte. Att göra studier som undersöker konsumenternas upplevelse är därför ett viktigt nästa steg för vidare studier.

Nyckelord: Matsvinn, förpackningar, smart förpackning, gasindikator, mathandel.

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1 Introduction

It is too easy - to buy something new to eat for dinner, rather than eat the leftovers in the fridge. Or, to pour out the milk that has been standing in the fridge two days after its expiration date. And did that chicken really seem good? Better safe than sorry, a vice that unfortunately directs a lot of food to the trash instead of being eaten. Not having time to plan what to eat due to a stressful work-life balance, in combination with misleading promotions at the supermarket, urging us to “buy more to save money”, often leads to unnecessary purchases that often become waste rather than a nice meal (Wikström, Williams, 2023). As an individual, it is also tempting to wonder about the relevance of these small actions, what does it matter if I eat this last slice of bread or toss it? In short - it matters.

A common estimation is that, globally, a third of the produced food is discarded (United Nations Environment Programme, 2021), and some of the later studies estimate a waste level as high as 40% (Wikström, Williams, 2023). Producing all this food takes its toll on the environment. Agriculture requires significant amounts of land, energy and resources and contributes to environmental issues such as eutrophication and greenhouse gas emissions. In Sweden, it is the third largest source of carbon dioxide emissions, accounting for around 14% of total emissions (Naturvårdsverket, 2024). Somewhat simplified - if a third is discarded, it means that a third of the environmental impact of agriculture goes to produce food that is of no use. Efforts to tackle food waste have therefore become a global priority, as reflected in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 12, Sustainable Consumption and Production (United Nations, 2015). Target 12.3 aims to halve global food waste at the retail and consumer levels by 2030. Achieving this ambitious goal requires action across multiple sectors, including retailers, businesses, and individual consumers.

According to the latest statistics on food waste in Sweden (Naturvårdsverket, 2023), households account for the largest part of waste generation, around 48%. The waste from food retailers was estimated at 7%. Although it is a smaller fraction of food waste, it could be argued that retail waste contains only edible food (Naturvårdsverket, 2023). Retailers therefore have a responsibility to decrease their food waste.

Two authors who have conducted extensive research in the area are Fredrik Wikström and Helén Williams (2023). They note that two consumer needs are particularly relevant for reducing food waste: (1) the ability to buy the right amount of food to meet their needs and (2) the ability to determine when food has actually gone bad (Wikström, Williams, 2023). Both of these factors can be connected to the packaging. Designing packaging with careful considerations to food waste is therefore something the authors argue for. According to their findings, a third of the food waste in households could be avoided with better packaging corresponding to consumer needs.

One promising solution to solve this second problem stated by Wikström, Williams (2023) is by providing the consumers with more information about the status of the food. New types of packaging are therefore under development, so-called intelligent or smart packaging. Smart packaging adds functions to the packaging, beyond the normal tasks of protection and conservation (Müller et al., 2019). One type of this is a gas indicator, which can chemically react when the presence of gases typical for bacterial growth has reached a critical level. If such a sensor could signal to the consumer that the product is still good, perhaps it could motivate the consumer to eat the food rather than waste it, maybe even after the expiration date has passed.

1.1 Research questions

The aim of this thesis is to explore what potential smart packaging has in reducing food waste, and the total environmental impact of the eaten amount of food.

This aim could be investigated in many different ways, and therefore, there is a need to limit the scope by selecting research approaches. The first approach will be centered around theoretical calculations of the environmental performance of a smart packaging innovation, using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), and relate that to different levels of waste reduction. The first research question is:

- RQ1: Is there a scenario where smart packaging reduces the total environmental impact of a packed food product, by means of reduction in food waste?

This first research questions asks if there could be a hypothetical environmental net "win" by using smart packaging to reduce waste, that is that even though the packaging adds environmental impact, the total impact on on a system level is decreased. This question searches for a theoretical answer, but for these potential improvement to be realized, the innovation also needs to be implemented in an actual system. The package will interact with different actors in the food chain from that the packaging is introduced. A systematic overview of these actors is presented in figure 1.

Figure 1: A conceptual figure over the potential actors who would interact with a smart packaging.

The smart packaging's interaction with the food chain starts where the product is packed at industry, after which a logistic chain takes place, either to an intermediate warehouse or direct to store (in the image this is simplified to a direct transport to store). After the transport the product enters a store, where it is either sold or wasted. The sold part of the product reaches the household, and is either discarded without being used or cooked into a meal. It may be noted that the product in itself can also be discarded after cooking, but this waste stream is not relevant for the packaging system, since the smart packaging only is meant to reduce waste before the food is cooked.

The actors who interact with the packaging are producers, logistics, retailers and consumers. In order to

study the entrance of a smart packaging on the market, all of these could be of interest. According to the latest statistics for food waste in Sweden, the food waste is the largest in the households, with 48% of the total food waste, while food retailers stands for 7% of the total waste (Naturvårdsverket, 2023). However, in order for the smart product to reach the consumer, the product has to be sold in food stores. The retailers are in that sense gate-keepers to the introduction of the product. The retailers also has a large influence on what is offered to the consumers, as a few companies dominate the market (Kulikovskaja et al., 2017). These facts makes the retailers highly interesting to study, especially since there are few studies that investigates retailers reaction to smart packaging. The consumers and their behavior on the other hand is a rather well-investigated area. By deepening the understanding of the retailers' perspective, the possible barriers and potentials for a smart packaging solution to reduce food waste can be understood better. The second research question is therefore:

- RQ2: What potentials and barriers do the retailers see for a smart packaging to reduce food waste? And what potentials and barriers are reflected in the way they work with food waste and packaging today?

1.2 Delimitations

The aim of this study is broad, and two ways to assess it have been defined. It is possible that there exists other ways to asses this question and the choice of method affects the results and conclusions that are possible to draw. Therefore, some limitations will be presented. Since two methods were used within this project, both methods are limited in time and resources, in comparison if either had been performed alone.

For the life cycle assessment, both the extent and the quality is highly affected by the available resources and time. An LCA often require multiple iterations and rounds of data collection. In this thesis, the data collection could not be too time consuming, so assumptions was necessary where data was lacking. This affects the results and will be further commented in the discussion section.

In the interview study, the number of interviewees had to be limited, with respect to the time demand of performing and analyzing interviews. The retailer perspective will therefore be represented by two types of experts, food waste experts and packaging experts. Ideally, more actors from the retailing world could have been interviewed to get a more diverse perspective from the entire retailing chain. In this study, the perspective will be limited to that of the two types of experts and to the Swedish retailing sector.

2 Background to food waste and packaging

Depending on where in the food chain the waste occurs, it is referred to with different terms, that is either food loss or food waste. Food loss is used to describe food that is of edible quality, but for some reason leaves the food chain before the retail stage and which is not redirected for other purposes, for example animal feed. An example of this could be potatoes that do not meet the quality standards for sale and are plowed to the soil rather than redirected for other purposes (Wikström, Williams, 2023). Food that is discarded at and after the retailers is called food waste. Food waste can be split into edible and un-edible fractions. This separation is necessary when discussing avoidable food waste, where efforts to reduce waste are the most important. But what is edible and not might differ in opinion and culture, for example if potato skin and carrot peel is edible or not. These types of differences can cause variation in the global measuring. For each new study, it is not uncommon to see that the waste level is often increased, because more streams are identified (United Nations Environment Programme, 2021; Wikström, Williams, 2023; Naturvårdsverket, 2023).

According to United Nations Environment Programme, 2021 the stage where the majority of waste occurs differs between low- and high-income countries. In low-income countries, more food is lost during the early stages of the food chain, such as harvesting and storage. In high-income countries, more of the waste occurs in the later stages, particularly in retail and among consumers. However, the data from the Food index report is not entirely robust for all countries, for some the data is very uncertain, such as Africa, while Europe has an higher data reliability.

In Sweden, the total food waste in 2022, including edible and inedible parts, was 1 420 000 tones, and 1 230 000 tones when excluding liquid waste. Of the solid food waste, the households generated the largest part of the waste, around 48%. Although this is a large fraction, it is worth mentioning that most meals are prepared in the households. The consumers are also affected by marketing and special offers that the retailers presents (Naturvårdsverket, 2023; Wikström, Williams, 2023). So, although the consumers stand for the largest fraction of the waste, they should not be seen as the sole responsible part in the fight to decrease food waste. The waste from retail was estimated to 7%. Although it is a smaller fraction of the food waste, the retailer waste could be argued to contain only edible food, according to Naturvårdsverket (2023). Retailers therefore have an important responsibility in decreasing their food waste.

Retailers and food waste reduction actions

Retailers are taking actions to reduce their food waste. As they have an important position, involving a lot of power over what is offered to the consumer, retailers have a responsibility, argues Kulikovskaja et al. (2017), who has performed an exploratory study on food waste avoidance actions in Denmark. One of the most common actions was to apply a price reduction of suboptimal food products, such as overripe fruits and vegetables, and to reduce the price on products close to expiry. Another common action was cooperation with charity organizations for food donations. The authors found that the food waste question has been given great focus in Denmark, and that performing these kind of food waste avoidance actions has become an industry norm, though different retailers engaged on different levels (Kulikovskaja et al., 2017).

Huang et al. (2021), who performed a systematic literature review of articles and gray literature concerning retailers food waste reduction actions, also found these actions to be abundant in the literature, and that there has been an increasing interest in the question of food waste reduction actions in the retailing world over the last 10 years. They observed that this reduction action coincides well with the retailer's interest

to maximize its economic win. Offering products close to expiry, to a lower price can give the retailers an income in comparison to wasting it. How much of these discounted products that are wasted in the home is uncertain, as few studies have examined it.

Wikström, Williams (2023) mentioned that marketing and deals which convince consumer to by “two for the price of one”, or similar sales tactic, can lead unnecessary purchase, which leads to more waste in the households. Some retailers have therefore gone so far in their ambition to reduce waste as to abolish multi-buy offers (Huang et al., 2021).

So, if retailers are working on their responsibility, what is important to do in order to achieve the same reduction at the household level? Two authors who have conducted extensive research in this are Fredrik Wikström and Helèn Williams. They have performed a lot of studies on the household level, by for example letting consumers fill out a food waste diary. One of their key findings is that packaging plays a critical role in food waste generation at the household level. They have summarized their findings from their studies in a popular science book called *Stop the food waste - a packaged solution* (Stoppa matsvinnet – en förpackad lösning). Wikström and Williams note that two consumer needs are particularly relevant for reducing food waste: (1) the ability to buy the right amount of food to meet their needs and (2) the ability to determine when food has actually gone bad (Wikström, Williams, 2023). Both factors can be connected to the packaging. Designing packaging with careful considerations to food waste is therefore something that the authors argue for. According to their findings, a third of the food waste in households could be avoided with better packaging corresponding to the consumers’ needs.

How packaging is related to food waste

The first problem, the ability to buy the right amount, can be solved by changing the size of the packaging. Wikström, Williams (2023) note that almost half of the households in Sweden are single person households, which is not well reflected in the packaging sizes available in the supermarkets. Also, a common misunderstanding by the consumer is that larger packaging is better for the environment, since it has more food per packaging. But this is a misconception; the food has a much higher environmental impact than the packaging, so buying a larger packaging and wasting some of the food is worse from an environmental perspective (Silvenius et al., 2014). This means that packaging designers have an important task in designing packaging that meets the needs of the consumers, but which also have a reasonable amount of materials. Wikström, Williams, Venkatesh (2016) frames it in this way: when designing packaging for the lowest possible environmental impact, it is either possible to look at the direct effects, which are the environmental performance of the materials, or the indirect effects, such as how the consumer handles the packaging and how the packaging affects food waste (Wikström, Williams, Venkatesh, 2016). The packaging that generates more food waste is the worst alternative from this perspective.

This inclusion of indirect effects has been illustrated in an earlier study by Wikström, Williams, Verghese, et al. (2014), where they investigate the consequences of neglecting food waste from the Life cycle assessment of a packaging. In a typical LCA of food packaging, only the materials for the packaging and their manufacturing is included (i.e the direct effects). In this strategy, minimizing the environmental impact of the product is often equal to reducing the amount of materials; packaging with less material are thereby favored. But this type of low material packaging might not correspond to the need the consumer has. Low-material packaging might also have worse protective properties. The authors argue that this increased risk for food waste should be attributed to the environmental impact of the packaging, and by that “upscaling” the functional unit of

the LCA to *eaten food*, rather than the more traditional “ability to pack a certain amount of food”. In such an LCA study, the packaging that results in the least food waste is the most environmentally sound one. To illuminate the effect of this upscaling, the authors have performed a simple scenario LCA-study with two food products in three types of packaging, each having a different estimated amount of food wasted per packaging. The food products are rice, with a relatively high climate impact, and yogurt which has a lower climate impact in comparison to rice. Wikström, Williams, Verghese, et al. (2014) found that, if assuming that all three alternative packaging are recycled, food waste was the deciding factor for the environmental impact of the packaging. They also state that a packaging change which decreases food waste is almost always motivated. The authors identify the need for the packaging to “contain the correct dose” as an important parameter to reduce food waste. A key finding in this article is that for food with high climate impact “*almost any packaging measure that can reduce waste would be worthwhile from a climate perspective, regardless of the waste treatment system*” (Wikström, Williams, Verghese, et al., 2014).

A similar finding was made by Shrivastava et al. (2022), who looked at the impact of wrapping cucumbers in plastic. They concluded that, for the studied system of cucumbers from Spain transported to Austria, using plastic to decrease food waste can have a net positive effect. The environmental impact of the plastic wrap, in global warming potential (GWP), corresponds to the GWP of 93 cucumbers. Saving only 1.1% of cucumbers in the plastic system resulted in a net positive effect, in comparison to the unwrapped system. This means that even though the packaging adds an environmental cost, the food waste reduction can still lead to a net positive effect in global warming potential, when looking at the food- and packaging system as one. This is somewhat contradictory to the strategy of reducing the packaging material as much as possible.

An important term when discussing how packaging can mitigate food waste is extended shelf life. By prolonging the amount of time before the food spoils, or the time until the date mark is reached, less food could be wasted. Casson et al. (2022) illustrated this in a LCA-study for three kinds of packaging solutions for beef. In their method they compared two more technically advanced methods of packaging for sliced beef with a baseline packaging. The innovative packaging was vacuum skin, packaging in airtight plastic skin, and modified atmosphere packaging (MAP), where gas is injected into the package to prevent spoiling. The assumed baseline was a Styrofoam tray with plastic wrap. The results indicate that the baseline packaging had the best environmental performance in the direct perspective, as it contains less materials which gives a lower environmental impact, similar to what Wikström, Williams, Verghese, et al. (2014) stated when only accounting for the direct affects. Adding the indirect effects, that is the food waste generation per packaging, the baseline solution performed worse, as it had the shortest shelf life and resulted in more waste than the other packaging alternatives. Casson et al. (2022) states that the packaging system that gives the longest shelf life will result in the least food waste, and thereby also the lowest overall environmental impact if the product in itself has a high environmental burden, such as beef. In this case, the vacuum packaging and MAP were better alternatives, due to the longer shelf life.

From these examples of life cycle assessments, it is clear to see that the packaging can both be the cause of food waste, and the method to reduce it. Designing good packaging is really a key. Is it perhaps even possible to design packaging that has more functions that can help consumers avoid food waste? This brings the discussion to the second need that consumers have to reduce food waste: the ability to judge if the food is still good.

Could smarter packaging be part of the solution?

As mentioned, the second need the consumer has to reducing food waste is the ability to know if the food is still good (Wikström, Williams, 2023). Packaging plays an important role in reducing food waste by providing protection, as a physical barrier protects products from mechanical damage and biological degradation (Müller et al., 2019). In addition, packaging serves as a platform for communication, offering consumers information about the product and information about its expected shelf life. But, despite advances in packaging technology, once a product is sealed, the natural process of decay begins. The rate of this degradation varies depending on the product and the packaging method used, as well as the storage temperature. However, this gradual deterioration can be difficult for consumers to detect (Müller et al., 2019; Wikström, Williams, 2023). Even minor changes in appearance or the mere passing of a "best-before" date can lead consumers to prematurely discard food.

One promising solution to this issue is by providing the consumers with more information about the status of the food. Therefore, new types of packaging are being developed, so called intelligent or smart packaging. Smart packaging adds a function to the packaging, beyond the normal tasks of protection and conservation (Müller et al., 2019). One type of smart packaging that can give such information to the consumer is sensors and indicators. One type is called time-temperature indicators, which based on the storing temperature and number of passed days, can indicate to the consumer how many days there are left before the product spoils (Müller et al., 2019). These types of sensors are based on standardized calculations of the duration and does not actually measure more than the storing temperature. A more sophisticated type of smart packaging is gas sensors. A gas sensor can react to the atmosphere within the packaging, and detect chemical metabolites typical for bacterial growth (Müller et al., 2019), such as sulfur-containing compounds (Luo et al., 2022). These gas sensors can give a live update on the status of the food. If such a sensor can signal to the consumer that the product is still good, perhaps it could motivate the consumer to eat the food, rather than waste it, maybe even after the expiration date has passed. Perhaps this could be an alternative for skeptical consumers, such as the ones mentioned by Wikström, Williams (2023) who trusts the date marking without thinking twice.

One product which has a high risk of being prematurely disposed of is fresh chicken. Chicken is more likely to contain harmful bacteria in comparison to beef and pork, such as *Campylobacter jejuni*. Due to this, fresh chicken must be sold with a use-by date, according to EU-regulation (Livsmedelsverket, 2024). But, Söderqvist et al. (2024) mentions that *Campylobacter jejuni* does not grow at the recommended storage temperature, so the shelf life could hypothetically be extended. In their study Söderqvist et al. (2024) performed bacterial growth test on fresh chicken breasts and and a sensory test of cooked chicken. In the sensory test (taste test), they did not find any significant difference between chicken stored at the recommended temperature at its use-by date and four days after. The authors therefore suggest that the chicken could be marked more flexible than with the use-by date, but that further studies are needed, especially on raw chicken and consumer perception of off odors. They also mention that gas sensors could be a potential way to monitor the spoilage of chicken.

3 Case study of smart packaging

In order to explore the theoretical potential of smart packaging for reducing food waste, a case study has been performed. A new smart packaging innovation, which is currently under development was selected. This innovative packaging contains a so called biosensor which can indicate if a high level of bacterial growth. The biosensor reacts to gases within the atmosphere of the packaging, such as sulfur-rich volatile compounds, typical for bacterial activity. The sensor therefore requires a modified atmosphere packaging (MAP), where there is an airspace within the packaging. The biosensor is meant to be used in packaging for fresh meats, such as fresh chicken and minced meats ¹. The innovation is aimed both at retailers and consumers, with the goal of reducing food waste by informing the consumers (or retailers) when the product is still good enough to eat, even after best-before or use-by date has passed. This packaging innovation is part of a larger EU-project, named MICROORC, revolved around developing future packaging solutions to tackle food waste, where Research institute of Sweden (RISE) is responsible for the environmental assessment of the developed technologies. In figure 2, a conceptual image of the packaging is presented, and figure 3 shows conceptual image of the what the biosensor looks like and how it operates.

Figure 2: Conceptual figure of the smart packaging for chicken.

As presented in figure 3, a high concentration of gasses typical for bacterial growth will make an indicator on the sensor turn from white to brown. The sensor is constructed as a sticker and sits on the inside of the cover plastic for a packaging with plastic tray and cover plastic. This label, which shows the color change, is placed on the front of the packaging, so the consumer is informed when the product is no longer good enough to eat.

In this thesis, this innovation will be studied in the application for a packaging intended for fresh chicken. As mentioned in the introduction, chicken is a sensitive product with short shelf life. A recent study has highlighted that there is a need to evaluate dynamic labeling options for this product (Söderqvist et al., 2024). It is therefore of interest to examine new methods to determine the shelf life of chicken, to decrease unnecessary waste. Chicken is also the studied products within the scope of the EU-project that this innovation participates in. These are the reasons for selecting chicken as the packed product for this thesis.

¹Personal communication with Erik Månsson the 20th August 2024

Figure 3: Conceptual image of the biosensor and its mode of operation.

4 Methods

In order to explore the potential smart packaging has in reducing food waste, and the total environmental impact of the eaten amount of food, two research approaches have been defined for this thesis. The first research approach asks if it is possible to reach a scenario where smart packaging leads to a reduction in food waste to such an extent that the total environmental impact of the product-packaging system is decreased, compared to the baseline packaging and waste level. To investigate this question, a case study has been constructed, in which the environmental impact is estimated through life cycle assessment (LCA). The method for this LCA study is described in Section 4.1.

The second approach to investigate the potential of smart packaging, was to make inquiries of how such an innovation interacts with the reality in the food chain (figure 1). The second research question therefore focuses on the perspective from representatives in the retailing sector through interviews. The method for the interview study is described in Section 4.2.

4.1 Method to the LCA study

The method of the LCA case study aims to follow the recommendations expressed in the LCA standard ISO 14044. Acknowledging that this is a work performed within the limits of a student master thesis, the time, resources and skills in performing the LCA has been restricted. The results should therefore be interpreted with caution and with awareness to the uncertainty these restrictions brings about.

According to ISO 14044, a life cycle assessment should include four main parts: definition of goal and scope, Life cycle inventory (LCI) and an impact assessment, and interpretation. The tree aforementioned are presented in the following sections. The interpretation is made in the discussion section of this thesis.

4.1.1 Goal and scope of the LCA study

The goal of the LCA study is to evaluate the environmental impact of 1 kg of packed, fresh chicken under different waste scenarios, and comparing between a baseline packaging and a smart packaging. The results will be used in the discussion of this thesis to evaluate if the smart packaging has a potential to decrease the

total environmental impact of a packed chicken product, by reducing the food waste level. According to the LCA ISO standard, ISO 140 44, the authors should state the intended audience, and declare if the results from the LCA analysis will be used to make comparative environmental declarations. Such is not the case for this study. The comparison is only made between two types of packaging, not two different products. The intended audience for this LCA is the interested reader, the project partners within the MICROORC project and RISE.

Scope of the LCA Study

The scope of the LCA study should include information about the studied product system, the functional unit and the system boundaries.

Functional unit

The functional unit is 1 kg of eaten fresh chicken, and its packaging. Inspired by Wikström, Williams, Vergheese, et al. (2014), the functional unit is amount of *eaten* food, where the food waste fraction is attributed to the amount of eaten food, thereby adding the environmental impact of the wasted food units to the consumed units. This will be further explained in the coming section 4.1.3

System boundary

The system boundary in this LCA was cradle to gate, meaning that all actions up to the point where the chicken is ready to be packed, with or without the sensor, is included. The distribution chain, retailing step and consumer stage is therefore left outside the life cycle inventory. Instead, the effects of food waste is investigated by scaling the impacts from the product, up to the point of package, by the relevant waste fraction.

One exception to this system boundary has been necessary, due to limitations in available information: The energy use for the assembly process of the packaging has been excluded. The reason for excluding the production energy is that the sensor is for the time being manufactured by hand at lab-scale. It was not possible to receive information about the energy consumption of the lab, and more activity than only sensor production was performed at this site, with a minority of the activity being the production. For a larger scale production scenario, the manufacturing process should of course be considered. Not adding the energy use of the manufacturing process for neither the sensor nor final assembly could affect the results in a non-conservative way, since the total energy demand for the manufacturing process is underestimated. In the interpretation of the LCA results, this shortcoming and its effect on the overall results will be discussed.

Environmental impact assessment

The environmental impact of the system is calculated using the computer program SimaPro, using the method of Environmental Footprinting 3.1 (EF 3.1). Access was to SimaPro was provided by RISE, who has access to multiple databases for inventory data through this program. The utilized databases is described in the following section.

Concerning which environmental impact categories that were studied, a decision to not limit the number of categories at was made. Since there are no prior studies which investigates a similar gas-sensor technology, the LCA is highly exploratory. It is therefore of interest to screen the impacts in all possible impact categories.

Not all impacts might be relevant for the interpretation, but since it is hard to, à priori, judge which categories the sensor might have a substantial impact within, all possible impact categories in the EF 3.1 method will be calculated. These are summarized in table 1.

Table 1: The studied impact categories and their units.

Impact category	Unit	Explanation of abbreviations
Acidification	mol H + eq.	mol of hydrogen ion equivalents
Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq.	kg carbon dioxide equivalents
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	comparative toxic units for ecosystems
Particulate matter	disease inc.	disease increase
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq.	kg Nitrogen equivalents
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq.	kg Potassium equivalents
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq.	mol Nitrogen equivalents
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	comparative toxic units for humans
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	comparative toxic units for humans
Ionizing radiation	kBq U-235 eq	equivalent of kilobecquerels of Uranium 235
Land use	Pt	Points
Ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq.	kg of CFC-11 equivalent
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	kg of non-methane volatile organic carbons equivalents
Resource use, fossils	MJ	Mega Joules
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb eq	kg antimony equivalents
Water use	m ³ deprivation	cubic meter deprivation

In the interpretation of the results, special focus will be paid to the impact categories: Climate change, Eutrophication, Water use and Land use, since these are categories which agriculture often have an important effect within.

4.1.2 Life Cycle Inventory - LCI

The sensor is constructed of multiple materials, glued together to form the sensor-sticker. A conceptual image of the sensor and its layers can be seen in figure 4.

The information about the sensor and the necessary data for the LCA was acquired through online meetings with the manufacturing company, who offered data sheets for the materials used to produce the sensor. With the information provided on these data sheets, and knowing the dimensions of the finished sensor, the density and thickness on the sheets could be used to calculate the weight of the contributing material for a sensor. In table 2, the LCI-data for each layer in the sensor is presented, in grams. The inventory data for the chicken and packaging is summarized in table 3.

The calculations of the environmental impact was performed by using datasets in the database to SimaPro which RISE had access to. For the project, the databases that were used were EF 3.1, Ecoinvent and SIK FOOD DATABASE. The SIK food database is developed by RISE, and contained a dataset for Swedish

Figure 4: Conceptual figure of the Biosensor.

chicken fillets and a packaging for this type of chicken product, which were selected used in the LCA.

When choosing inventory data from the databases, an as close fit as possible to the original model was made, but finding a perfect fit was not always possible. For the scope of the LCA and this thesis, the closest fit was deemed worthy. In Appendix 1, a table summarizing the material choices for the sensor from the database in SimaPro is presented. The table also contains a comment on the data quality, with respect to representativeness. This data quality assessment was performed quantitatively, by comparing the material properties from the data sheet for the sensor materials and the metadata in the database.

4.1.3 Calculations and case setup

To answer the first research question, scenarios with different waste fractions has been constructed. The aim is to compare if a decrease in food waste in a system which includes the impact of the sensor can be lower than the impact of eaten food in the baseline packaging system.

In total, five scenarios has been investigated: two for retailer, two for household. In these separate scenarios for household and retail, it is of interest to know if a decrease in waste at either state separately could lead to a net positive environmental impact. Is it for example enough to reduce food waste at the retailers with 50% to reach a net positive impact? Or is a 10% reduction at household enough to reach a net positive effect. The two investigated scenarios at the retailers were a 50% waste reduction comparing to the current level, and a 100% reduction. For households, the two investigated reduction levels were 10% reduction and 50% reduction. Note that these two different stages have different waste fractions for chicken. The waste level for household was estimated from the literature (Sinkko et al., 2019) and the waste fraction from the retailer was found in the interviews.

Lastly, a theoretical best-case scenario was investigated, where the total waste level from both retail and consumer is compared to a 100% decrease of food waste, that is an abolishment of chicken food waste. The five scenarios are summarized in table 4. The retail scenarios are assigned an abbreviation with an R, household with an H, and the best case with R+H since it investigates an abolishment of waste at both

Table 2: LCI-data for the biosensor

Layer	Material	Weight [g]
1. Graphic layer		
1.1 Face stock	PP plastic film	0.18
1.2 Adhesive	Acrylic adhesive	0.057
1.3 Liner	PE / PET plastic laminate	0.14
2. Glue layer		
2.1 Paper	Super calendered paper	0.2
2.2 Glue	Rubber based adhesive	0.095
2.3 Paper	Super calendered paper	0.19
3. Sensor layer		
3.1 Carrier	Paper	0.001
3.2 Reagent	Organic chemical	0.00005
4. Membrane		
4.1 Membrane	Plastic non-woven pad	0.34

Table 3: LCI-data for the chicken and baseline packaging

Part	Material	Amount
Chicken		
Chicken fillets	Swedish chicken fillets	1 kg
Packaging		
Tray	PP plastic tray	20 g
Coverplastic	PP plastic film	0.026 m ²

stages simultaneously. For this best case scenario, a simple sensitivity analysis was also made. How this was performed is further described in the coming section 4.1.4.

The reason that the two investigated decrease levels were set differently between retailer and consumer is that it was judged difficult to reduce the waste level in the household with 100%. Studies has identified a risk that consumer misuses or misunderstand smart packing, observed by studies on consumer behavior concerning smart packaging (Obersteiner et al., 2021). The second reason is that it the retailer has a larger potential to make systematic changes in how they operate and handle waste on a store level, which could argue that it could be possible to reach a higher level of waste reduction. It is also of interest to know if a 100% reduction at retailer is enough to compensate for the added environmental impact of the biosensor. Also, the combined best case scenario covers the case where the waste is 100% reduced in both retail and household.

Table 4: Summary of the five case study scenarios and their waste levels.

Case	Description of change in waste level	Baseline waste level	Improvement waste level
Retailer scenarios			
R1	50% reduction of chicken food waste	3%	1.5%
R2	100% reduction of chicken food waste	3%	0%
Household scenarios			
H1	10% reduction of chicken food waste	11%	9.9%
H2	50% reduction of chicken food waste	11%	5.5%
Theoretical best case scenario			
R+H	100% reduction of chicken food waste at both retail and household	14%	0%

Calculations

To calculate the impact with the scenarios, some assumptions were made. The first assumption was that the impact of the *eaten food* can be calculated by scaling the impacts of the LCA results for the constituting parts. By doing this, the environmental impact of the food waste is added to the fraction of food that is eaten. This is a conceptual assumption, and could be argued to be too generalizing, but for the case of the study the method is judge as acceptable, especially as it corresponds well to the method used by Wikström, Williams, Verghese, et al. (2014).

The constituting parts in the baseline scenario is the chicken fillets and the packaging-tray and cover plastic (here referred as the baseline packaging), see equation 1. The innovation system also contains the impact of the sensor, see equation 2.

$$EI_{baseline,withoutFW} = EI_{chicken} + EI_{packaging} \quad (1)$$

$$EI_{innovation,withoutFW} = EI_{chicken} + EI_{packaging} + EI_{sensor} \quad (2)$$

The calculation of the total impact including food waste was calculated by multiplying the impacts described in equations 1 and 2 with the fraction for food waste, as expressed in equation 3. By varying the waste fractions f_i according to the case scenarios described table 4 the case scenarios were calculated.

$$EI_{scenario,i} = EI_{i,withoutfoodwaste} \cdot (1 + f_i) \quad (3)$$

After calculating the impact within the scenarios, the impact from the innovation and the baseline solutions were compared to find the possible improvement, in percent. The equation for this comparison is expressed in equation 4.

$$Improvement_i = \frac{EI_{baseline} - EI_{innovation_i}}{EI_{baseline}} \quad (4)$$

4.1.4 Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was conducted for the best-case scenario (R+H) to assess the sensitivity of the results for both the sensor and the chicken data. The purpose of this analysis was to evaluate the robustness of the results and to examine how variations in the system's input variables would influence the overall case calculation outcomes.

This sensitivity analysis was conducted separately for the sensor and the chicken data. The calculations were performed in Excel by applying a scaling factor to the original LCA results for the chicken or the sensor. If s is the investigated increase, these increased LCA results are calculated according to equation 5 and 6. The increased LCA results for these parts were then entered into the equations to calculate the case results (see equation 1 to 4). The results were tested for an increase of 10%, to see the effects a little variation in input data would have on the case results.

For the climate impact category, Rysselberge et al. (2021) found that there is a spread in LCA results for Swedish chicken, varying between 2.8 and 3 kg of CO₂ for some studies. This is higher than the selected data from the RISE-database. The climate impact category was therefore tested for this higher level of impact, to see how it would affect the case calculation results.

$$EI'_{chicken} = (1 + s) \cdot EI_{chicken} \quad (5)$$

$$EI'_{sensor} = (1 + s) \cdot EI_{sensor} \quad (6)$$

4.2 Interview method

Performing an interview study can be both challenging and rewarding, and Kvale et al. (2009) mentions that an important aspect of performing a successful interview study is to plan the whole of it from the beginning. The authors comment that problems in the analyzing phase often stem from a weakness in the preparatory phases. Kvale et al. (2009) breaks down the interview study into seven stages of interview inquiry going through these stages in their work. The seven steps are:

1. Thematizing
2. Designing
3. Interviewing
4. Transcribing
5. Analyzing
6. Verifying
7. Reporting

By considering these steps, linearly or iteratively, the researcher might be able to maintain the engagement and original vision throughout the investigation. In the following section, the interview study performed in this thesis will be presented following these steps.

4.2.1 Thematizing the interview study

According to Kvale et al. (2009) the thematizing phase corresponds much to the introductory phase of this thesis, where the *why*, the *what* and *how* to the study is stated. The reason for performing interviews in this thesis is to broaden the technical perspective of the study to include a social perspective. An innovation which works in theory is never guaranteed to work in reality, where the functionality is complicated by the interaction with the user. A study that does not include the user perspective would therefore be more speculative and not address the actual potential to reduce food waste in reality. Ideally, the perspective from both the consumer and the retailer should be investigated, but in regard of the time- and resource limitation this thesis has been performed under, only one of these could be included. As argued in the introduction, there is already knowledge and studies about consumer behavior and food waste, as well as studies on consumer reactions to smart packaging innovations (Henchion et al., 2019). The perspective of the retailers, on the other hand, maintain less investigated (Kulikovskaja et al., 2017). By gaining the perspectives on how retailers work with food waste and packaging internally, the goal is to be able to learn more about this interaction of innovation and reality. This insight would also be of a novel kind. A second reason for performing the interviews with the retailers was to obtain data on the waste level on chicken for the LCA analysis.

4.2.2 Designing the interview study

In the designing phase, prior knowledge of the field should be obtained (Kvale et al., 2009). This corresponds well to the background given in the introduction of this thesis, where knowledge from previous research within the area of food waste and packaging was presented. This knowledge has been the background to the creation of the interview study, especially the motivation to perform interviews with retailer rather than consumers, as stated earlier. The literature background has also been used to design the interview guide.

Selection of interviewees

To gain understanding of both the food waste and the packaging perspective from the retailers, the need to interview experts from both of these fields was recognized. The smart packaging innovation aims at reducing the food waste, so to interview the food waste expert was seen as the appropriate choice. Since the key to the waste reduction in the innovation lies in the function of the packaging, understanding how retailers think when designing packaging was seen as another area of interest. Recognizing this, the packaging experts from the retailer companies was also seen as a relevant candidate for the interviews. Ideally, some representatives from the floor, that is the actual stores, could have been included to broaden the perspective on how the innovation would integrate with the retailers business practices. Due to limitation in time, this was not possible. The perspectives from the packaging and food waste experts will therefore represent the perspective from retailers.

An important aspect of the interview design stage, according to Kvale et al. (2009), is to consider the moral implication of the interviews. Recognizing that statements about how the retailers handles waste, especially the amounts of waste generated, might be sensitive information in the eyes of the companies, all the interviewees and their company were decided to be kept anonymous. The anonymity was judged to not affect the results negatively, since the aim of the study is not to compare the strategies between the retailers, but rather to receive as much knowledge as possible of how the retailers handle the question off food waste and packaging.

From the existing retailers in Sweden, three were selected. The companies that were asked to participate

belong to the food retailers with the largest market share in Sweden. Besides this, a large reason for selecting them was that contacts at the companies already existed within RISE. A introductory email describing the purpose of the study and the aim of the interviews was sent to contacts at these retailers. The contacts to these three companies were acquired through a colleague at RISE. The primary contacts were not the people who in the end participated in the interviews, but they were able to forward the contact information of the relevant experts. All the of the invited experts consented to participating, none declined.

The interview guide

The interview questions were prepared by looking to the literature, to see what the core questions in connection was to food waste and packaging was. As the literature identifies a need to asses the question of packaging and food waste in unison (Wikström, Williams, Venkatesh, 2016), the interview guide included questions concerning both food waste and packaging, posed to both the food waste experts and the packaging experts.

Although, one of the central part of the interviews is to gain insight into the retailers thoughts on the possibilities of smart packaging to reduce food waste, the interview guide was designed to include more question that only related to the case. In order to truly understand and interpret the way the retailers think and by that answer the second research question, it was judged to be important to understand their current strategies. According to Huang et al. (2021) and Kulikovskaja et al. (2017) retailers already perform a number of measures to reduce and prevent food waste. Learning about these could therefore be important to the discussion of the smart packaging case as well in the following interview analysis. Similarly for the packaging experts, their packaging strategy was the first topic of the interview guide and intended to be used in a similar way in the case discussion and interview analysis.

Beside the two parts, (1) strategies and (2) case with smart packaging, two more sections were added to the interview guide. For the LCA study, there was a need to know how much food waste there is in the category fresh meat and fresh chicken. One section was therefore dedicated towards collecting those answers. This led to a semi-structured interview guide with four topics: (1) food waste and packaging strategy in the company, (2) food waste in numbers, (3) perspective on packaging and the expiration date-labeling system and finally (4) a discussion of the case of packaging with smart sensor.

4.2.3 Performing the interviews

The interviews were either performed in person or online. For one of the three companies, the interview with the two experts were held together.

The interviews followed the outline of interview guide in a semi structured manner, meaning that the order of the four sections was partly interchangeable, a decision often based on the answers given during the interview. Often, section (2) date mark and (3) packaging was interchangeable. The interviews always started with a presentation of the interviewee, followed by the questions concerning strategy in section (1). For the food waste experts, this referred to the food waste strategy, while the packaging experts were asked about the packaging strategy. For all the interviews, the case was presented last of all sections. The duration of the interview varied between 45 minutes and one hour.

With the interviewee's consent, the interviews were audio-recorded. One of the interviews were also video recorded through the online-meeting software, which allowed for automatic transcription.

4.2.4 Transcribing the interviews

The fourth phase in Kvale et al. (2009)'s framework, transcribing, is mentioned as an important part of the analyzing phase as the researcher gets in to know their material in depth. Practically, the interviews analysis was performed by listening to the audio recordings and noting important facts or quotes on a whiteboard in the three categories of the analysis framework. After the interviews had been summarized in this manner, the audio file was automatically transcribed using the Microsoft Word function to dictate. In the work of selecting quotes to match the key takeaways from the interviews, the rough transcription from Word was improved by manually transcribing the full quotes of interest. Since the interviews were performed in Swedish, the quotes were then translated, with caution so that as little meaning as possible would be lost in the translation.

4.2.5 Interview analysis

The interview's fifth step, analysis, can be performed in different ways, depending on the purpose, topic and on the nature of the study (Kvale et al., 2009). In the case of this study, an analytic framework was developed, see figure 5. The framework consisted of three main themes, which are (1) the strategies and priorities, (2) knowledge and work- overlap between the two types of experts and (3) the experts reaction to the smart packaging innovation.

Figure 5: Analytic framework for the interview analysis.

The first part of the analysis searched for the main strategies the retailer experts used to reach their goals, and the challenges their facing in reaching those goals. The second focus aimed to investigate if there was work-and knowledge overlap between the two experts. Wikström, Williams, Venkatesh (2016) commented on the importance for packaging experts to acknowledge the effects the packaging has on food waste. With this second analytic focus, the aim is to investigate if such overlaps exists, from either direction of expertise. In the third part of the analytic framework, the answers to the case questions is interpreted to see what potentials and barriers the retailers see for the smart packaging solution.

5 Results

The Results section is divided into two parts, the first presenting the results from the LCA study, and the second presenting the results from the interviews. The LCA results are presented in three subsections, where the first section 5.1.1 shortly presents the LCA results for the Biosensor. This section highlights what parts of the sensor gives addition to the impact. This information will then be used in the following discussion of the environmental impact of the total system, which is presented in the second section of the LCA results, section 5.1.2. The last part of the LCA results, section 5.1.3, presents the calculations for the smart packaging case study, where the LCA results from section 5.1.2 has been calculated with added level of waste, according to the waste scenarios described in table 4 of the method.

The second part of the results is devoted to the interview results. The interview results are divided into three sections corresponding to the three parts of the analysis framework presented in figure 5. In the first section, 5.2.1, the strategies and priorities in the retailers work with packaging and food waste is presented. In the second section, 5.2.2, the knowledge- and work overlap between the two areas is presented. The final part of the interview results, section 5.2.3, summarizes the retailers perspective of the smart packaging case.

5.1 LCA Results

The results from the LCA are presented in three sections. The first presents the environmental impact of the sensor itself. In the second section presents the environmental impact of the whole system, comparing the impact of the chicken, the packaging and the sensor. In the last section, the calculation of the case scenarios is presented.

5.1.1 LCA results for the biosensor

A relative presentation of the environmental impact of part of the biosensor is shown in figure 6. Since this is an exploratory studies, most impact categories have been kept. Throughout the report, not all impact categories will be commented in depth.

Two layers that often stands for a larger share of the impact is the glue layer (presented as dark green), and the graphic layer (presented as yellow). For land use, the glue layer clearly dominates the impact. The reason for this is that the glue is contained between two sheets of supercalendred paper, and the paper production is what gives a large addition to the land use impact. The impact from the sensor pad, containing the chemical reactant and a carrier, layer 3 in figure 4, is so small in comparison to the other parts that it is not visible in this graphical representation. That suggest that the sensor pad could have been excluded from the LCA.

Method: Environmental Footprint 3.1 (adapted) V1.01 / EF 3.1 normalization and weighting set / Characterization
 Analyzing 1 p '0 Biosensor';

Figure 6: Figure presenting the environmental impact of the sensor.

Method: Environmental Footprint 3.1 (adapted) V1.01 / EF 3.1 normalization and weighting set / Characterization
Analyzing 1 p 'Innoscentia chicken';

Figure 7: Relative additions of the parts of the chicken package system, including the biosensor.

5.1.2 LCA results for the system

The impact of all the parts of the smart chicken packaging, that is chicken, packaging and sensor, is presented in a comparative graph in figure 7.

As can be seen, the impact of the biosensor is often small in comparison to the other parts of the system. The chicken dominate the environmental impact in the categories climate change, particulate matter, ionizing radiation, resource use and water use. The packaging dominated the impact in the categories acidification, eutrophication, ozone depletion, photochemical oxidation as well as fossil resource use.

5.1.3 LCA results for the waste scenarios

The goal of performing the LCA study was to construct cases with different waste levels, with and without biosensor, and compare them to each other. In that way, the environmental performance of the packaging solution with the sensor can be evaluated and compared to the baseline scenario. This comparison is done both for both the retail and consumer waste level, as well as a combined best case scenario. The five scenarios are summarized in table 8 in the methods section.

The waste level in household was assumed to be 11% according to Sinkko et al. (2019). For the retail scenario, the waste level was based on information from the interviews. According to one of the retailers, the waste for fresh chicken was slightly above 3% in their stores. Another indicated vaguely that the fresh chicken waste was lower, closer to 1%. Since the first retailer agreed to show more data to support the claim, while the second did not, a waste level at 3% was assumed for the retailers.

In figure 8 the results from the case study is presented. The results are marked with colors, where the green marking indicate a result where the environmental impact of the smart system is lower than the impact of the baseline system, thanks to the reduced level of waste. The value is therefore negative. Ideally all cells should be green for the sensor system to be more environmentally sound than the baseline packaging. The red cells mark the results where the impact from the smart packaging system is higher than the baseline packaging, even for the decreased waste level. A third gray category has also been used, for results close to 0% change. Recognizing the uncertainties and limitation in the LCA, results between -2.5 to 2.5% change are marked with gray, to indicate that this result is close to no change between the improved and baseline scenario.

A note of the reliability of the results: The goal of this LCA is to perform comparative statements, such as the ones in figure 8. One advantage of doing these types of comparison rather than focusing solely on the absolute number is that the uncertainty in the model affects both parts being compared. In the case presented in table 4, the base line packaging is compared to an identical packaging which also contains a biosensor. The only difference between the cases is therefore the impact of the sensor and the waste factor. In that sense, the eventual shortcomings of the results are present in both the compared cases. The tray and cover plastic as well as the chicken exists both in the sensor case and in the base line. The largest uncertainty that could affect the results therefore lie in the modeling of the sensor. As can be seen in figure 7, the impact of the sensor is often small in comparison to the other parts.

In case R1, a 50% reduction of the food waste in retail thanks to the use of the biosensor is investigated. This reduces the total climate impact by one percent compared to the current base line case. It also reduces the water use impact by one percent, as well as ionizing radiation and ozone depletion. These are the only impact categories where the sensor (and resulting waste reduction) reduce the total environmental impact of

	Retail		Household		Best case
	R1	R2	H1	H2	R+H
	50% reduction Waste: 1.5%	100% reduction waste: 0%	10% reduction Waste: 8.9%	50% reduction Waste: 5.5%	100% reduction Waste: 0%
Acidification	2%	0%	2%	-2%	-10%
Climate change	-1%	-3%	-1%	-5%	-12%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	14%	12%	15%	10%	1%
Particulate matter	2%	1%	3%	-1%	-9%
Eutrophication, freshwater	2%	0%	2%	-2%	-10%
Eutrophication, terrestrial	2%	1%	3%	-1%	-9%
Human toxicity, cancer	24%	22%	24%	20%	10%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	11%	9%	12%	7%	-1%
Ionising radiation	-1%	-3%	-1%	-5%	-12%
Land use	16%	14%	16%	12%	3%
Ozone depletion	-1%	-3%	-1%	-5%	-12%
Photochemical ozone formation	3%	1%	3%	-1%	-9%
Resource use, fossils	1%	-1%	1%	-3%	-11%
Resource use, minerals and metals	3%	1%	3%	-1%	-9%
Water use	-1%	-3%	-1%	-5%	-13%

Figure 8: Summary of the improvement for the five cases, in comparison with the baseline scenario

the system. For the rest the impact is increased. For most categories, the impact is increased by 2-3%, but three categories stand out: Ecotoxicity for freshwater, Human toxicity for cancer and Land use. The largest increase in impact is seen in the human ecotoxicity-cancer, an increase of 24% compared to base line scenario. As previously mentioned, the glue layer is what contributes the most from the sensor to this category. From the packaging, both the material and processing for the tray has an effect in that category. Although the impact in relative numbers is increased by 24%, the absolute value of the impact in human toxicology is very small, being in the eleventh decimal for human toxicology (cancer). What the toxicology categories express is probabilities based on ecotoxicological equation, comparing risk of exposure and potentially affected fraction of the population (PAF) (Golsteijn, 2014). The results in these categories is therefore different from the other categories, and even more uncertain since it describes probabilities. Due to this, no further discussion will be held concerning the toxicity categories.

In the consumer case H1, with reduction of food waste with 10%, the impact is similar to the consumer R1, with only improvement within the climate change and water use categories by one percent. For the larger improvement at household level in case H2, with a 50% reduction in the waste, the total impact of the system reaches a better improvement, where climate change is reduced by 5% as well as water use. All of the eutrophication categories are also improved a little. Generally, in comparison to the best case in retailing, the consumer best case has more improvement, but it remains bellow 5%. Also for the household case, the impact in Land use, Human toxicology and ecotoxicity increased in comparison to the base line scenario.

The last column in table 8 is the combined best-of case, where the current total waste from household and retail waste, of 14.3%, is compared to a 100% reduction of waste with the innovation. In this calculation, the absolute best improvement the sensor innovation can achieve is therefore shown. In this case, an improvement can be seen for all the impact categories except ecotoxicity, human toxicity-cancer and land use. The improvement is 12% for climate change, around 10% for the eutrophication categories and 13% for water use. For land use change, the impact is on the other hand increased by 3%.

5.1.4 Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was performed for both the sensor and chicken data. The sensitivity analysis was performed by scaling the LCA results in all impact categories by 10% and comparing the new results to the original result for the case calculations for R+H. Although this might be a simple method, it can give some informing indications. The change in the results for the sensor is presented in figure 9 and for the chicken in figure 10

When adding 10% impact to each category of the sensor, the results for scenario R+H mainly remained unchanged. The only categories where the percentual change between the baseline scenario and the improved scenario differed were ecotoxicity, human toxicity for cancer and non-cancer, and land use. This might not be too surprising, as it is within these categories that the sensor had a relatively large addition to the system in comparison to the packaging and the chicken, as seen In the comparative graph 7.

	Sensitivity analysis Sensor		
	R+H	R+H(s)'	Change
	Original results	10% increase in all sensor impacts	Change from original results
Acidification	-10%	-9%	0%
Climate change	-12%	-12%	0%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	1%	3%	1%
Particulate matter	-9%	-9%	0%
Eutrophication, freshwater	-10%	-9%	0%
Eutrophication, terrestrial	-9%	-9%	0%
Human toxicity, cancer	10%	12%	2%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	-1%	0%	1%
Ionising radiation	-12%	-12%	0%
Land use	3%	4%	2%
Ozone depletion	-12%	-12%	0%
Photochemical ozone formation	-9%	-8%	0%
Resource use, fossils	-11%	-11%	0%
Resource use, minerals and metals	-9%	-8%	0%
Water use	-13%	-13%	0%

Figure 9: Sensitivity analysis for changes in the sensor data, by 10% increase.

Similar to the sensitivity to changes for the sensor data, when increasing the impact of the chicken data with 10% the results for scenario R+H mainly remained unchanged. Once again the only change occurs within the categories Ecotoxicity, human toxicology for cancer and non-cancer, and land use. In a third sensitivity analysis, the climate data for chicken was increased to match the size of a danish dataset from the RISE-database, where the climate impact was estimated to 5 kg of CO₂ per kg chicken. Even for this large increase, the climate impact remained at -12% change for scenario R+H.

To test the robustness of the climate change impact category, this category was tested again for higher climate impact. By increasing the climate impact to 3 kg CO₂ per kilogram of chicken, according to the highest average for Swedish chicken identified by Rysselberge et al. (2021). Also for this data, the relative improvement remained at 12% reduction in the best-case scenario.

	Sensitivity analysis Chicken		
	R+H	R+H(c)'	Change
	Original results	10% increase in all chicken impacts	Change from original results
Acidification	-10%	-10%	0%
Climate change	-12%	-12%	0%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	1%	1%	-1%
Particulate matter	-9%	-9%	0%
Eutrophication, freshwater	-10%	-10%	0%
Eutrophication, terrestrial	-9%	-9%	0%
Human toxicity, cancer	10%	9%	-1%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	-1%	-2%	-1%
Ionising radiation	-12%	-12%	0%
Land use	3%	2%	-1%
Ozone depletion	-12%	-12%	0%
Photochemical ozone formation	-9%	-9%	0%
Resource use, fossils	-11%	-11%	0%
Resource use, minerals and metals	-9%	-9%	0%
Water use	-13%	-13%	0%

Figure 10: Sensitivity analysis for changes in the chicken data, by 10% increase.

5.2 Interview results

The interview analysis was performed according to the questions presented in figure 5. Following the three parts of the analytic framework, the results are summarized in figure 11. In the following sections, these points will be further explained and related to quotes from the interviewees.

For each finding, a quote from an interviewee is presented. The quotes are presented with an abbreviation to indicate if it is a food waste (FW) or packaging (PAC) expert who said the quote. The three retailing companies are called A, B and C, which have no connection to their real names. For example, a food waste expert from company A is presented as “A-FW” and a packaging expert from company B is presented as “B-PAC”.

5.2.1 Strategies and priorities

The first theme in the interview analysis was strategies and priorities for the retailers. This theme was divided into main focuses, prioritized questions and challenges. The main focuses for all the three retailers was similar, for both types of experts. The main focuses were:

- Data as a way to work strategically
- Business mutual goals for food waste reduction
- Business mutual goals for plastic reduction

Data as a way to work strategically

For both the packaging strategy and the food waste strategy, data played a central role. By looking at data for food waste levels or packaging specifications, focus areas could be identified and strategies developed. For two of the three retailers, it was clear that their work with food waste management as well as packaging was systematic and highly prioritized in the company. The third also saw these questions as important, but had

Figure 11: Interview results summarized according to the analytic framework.

not yet developed as a clear structure for how to work with the questions on a strategic level.

For food waste management, the data collection is done manually with a handheld computer by retail workers, using codes for different causes for waste. Examples of some codes are short date, expired, crushed or faulty product. Since having data for the food waste was so important for the strategic work, the food waste experts saw this as a prioritized question:

FW-B: "Right now there is still a problem with registration the waste on the correct code, so that is a big prioritization for us[...] All stores must put down the work, because it will become a win in the long run."

The work to collect data at the retailers concerning food waste had been going on for a longer time, but data collection was more novel for the packaging experts. According to retailer A, the data collection was something they had accelerated a lot over the latest years:

A-PAC: A big part of what we have done over the past four years is that we have collected data. When I first came in, we basically had no knowledge about our packaging. [...] We had a fairly good understanding, and we were steering in the right direction as best as we could, but we had nothing to work strategically with. So we started collecting data. [...] It was quite a substantial preparatory phase where we really had to narrow down our sustainability goals—what we should measure and what we should focus on. [...] Now, four years later, we are at about 94% completed data.

This data was used to make strategic decisions, and as implicated by A-PAC in the quote above, the data is used to find the relevant areas for further work. By using data to navigate, the retailers expressed an agile work style. The area of packaging has during the last years been affected by multiple new laws, and B-PAC therefore explained that the strategy was seen as dynamic:

B-PAC: There are constantly new guidelines and documentation coming, on how packaging should be designed to be recyclable, for example, and we will need to adapt to that. This strategy [...] is a living document because we don't believe it [the situation] is static.

Business mutual goals

The goal for the food waste experts was to halve the food waste in comparison to the base line year 2016. Two of the three retailers claimed that they were on track with reaching this goal, thanks to the actions they had been implementing over the last couple of years. The most common and efficient way to reduce the waste was to reduce the price on items nearing expiry. Another alternative was to use the food internally to make dishes in the deli and sell it for lunch. Another alternative was to donate the food to humanitarian organizations.

The packaging experts had two main goals as well, both were related to plastics. They state that all packaging should be 100% recyclable by 2025 and that by 2030 all packaging should be made of renewable plastic. These goals were set by and agreed upon for all retailers in Sweden, through a common retailer cooperation organization. Unlike the food waste goals, the packaging experts did not expect to reach either of the two goals:

A-PAC: So far, we have based our efforts on our sustainability goals, which state that we should have recyclable packaging by 2025. [...] And that won't be achieved. No, it's not possible—because that goal was set for 100% recyclable packaging by 2025, and there are many types of packaging that don't meet that standard.[...] And then we have two goals set for 2030, which are about using recycled raw materials. We aim for, I believe, 100% recycled or renewable materials.[...] And we're also going to miss that target. So yes, we're struggling a bit. We've made good progress, and we've really made changes, especially with our efforts to reduce plastic, but it's tough.

One reason for the strong focus to reduce plastics is the new European legislation called the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR). The effects of this regulation was described as huge by the same interviewee:

A-PAC: Recently, a lot [of my work] has been about reading new legislation. There's a new major law coming called the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), and it will, how should I put it, almost knock over the industry in a way. [...] So we will have a lot to do, really a lot, and we are currently reading and immersing us in it together in the industry.

A challenge for the packaging experts was therefore to change the packaging for its own products to comply with the requirements of PPWR. One of the main requirements is that all packaging has to be recyclable by 2030, to be allowed to be sold. This was a large challenge, which creates a conflict of interest between food waste and packaging areas. These types of conflicts are the focus of the next part on the interview results.

5.2.2 Knowledge- and work exchange between food waste and packaging experts

The second analysis question concerned how the two areas of expertise cooperate or overlap in the work at the retailers and how food waste influences the work for the packaging expert and vice versa.

The interview results show that the packaging experts had a stronger understanding of- and relation to the food waste question, than the food waste experts understood their connection to packaging. Following

the effects of PPWR, the packaging experts found themselves in a especially tough bind to reach both the requirement in the directive and to design the best packaging to minimize (or at least not increase the food waste):

A-PAC: We've put up a good fight, [...] but it's tough. One of the reasons is really that food waste is paramount. For example, when packaging vacuum-packed meat, it's incredibly effective with a laminate, and it extends the shelf life of the meat by multiple days, and the meat has such a high climate impact. [...] We can work on the laminate and improve it, but we can't get all the way there. We still end up with waste at the end, like— what do we do with this if we don't have chemical recycling? And we're not really there yet. [...] And with this new legislation coming, it states that we should have recyclable packaging, but one can really wonder if they're thinking about food waste. Because it's not an equation that adds up right now. Maybe with technological development, but not at this moment.

In this quote, A-PAC clearly explains an understanding for both the questions related to packaging and food waste. This typ of understanding for complexity and conflicts of interested was expressed by the packaging expert at retailer B:

B-PAC: [...] often packaging, and especially plastic, gets a bad reputation. Many people have a strong aversion to plastic and believe it has a significant negative impact on the product itself. However, that's not the case. [...] It's not plastic that is the worst for the climate; it's far worse for food to be thrown away. [...] I sometimes feel that plastic gets an undeserved negative reputation considering the job it does.

The packaging expert at retailer C also expressed understanding for the complexity tied to packaging and food waste, but reflected that there are many important aspect to acknowledge in the design process. One rule was to never create more food waste:

C-PAC: There are several factors at play, but when we have a packaging that we need to develop or improve, we rarely make it worse in that [food waste] respect. That's just not how we do. It's not a written rule I think, but that's our approach. We don't do anything that worsens the issue of food waste or food safety. However, there are more factors involved [in packaging development], and food waste is just one of them.

Both the packaging experts at retailer A and B, stated that they had a rule that they should never create more food waste if making changes to the packaging. But as C-PAC mentioned, designing the packaging is often about balancing a lot of different factors, for example the shelf life:

A-PAC: Food waste is superior; we shall not create more food waste. However, there might be situations where you need to choose between two materials and end up with two days less shelf life for one of them. Then you have to weigh which product it is and how long it will sit on the shelf, and so on...

All in all, the packaging experts often had a complex understanding of how the packaging and food waste question interconnected. The rule to not create more food waste was a centerpieces of that. On the other hand, none of them mentioned working *proactively* with packaging to reduce food waste. Rather, the rule seemed to focus on not making the situation wore, that is maintaining status quo for the waste level.

The food waste experts had less to say about packaging issue, compared to how much the packaging experts

could say about the food waste issue. Often they recommended to save the questions to the interviews with the packaging experts. But since the overlap of understanding is important in this research focus, questions on packaging was posed to them as well, no matter their recommendations.

B-FW saw the packaging question as important and identified multiple reasons for why, but did not work so much with packaging themselves. This was true for all retailers, that none of the interviewed packaging and food waste experts worked together officially. At retailer A and B, colleagues to the interviewees worked together, but their role was in both cases more related to product development than food waste. The experts at retailer C said that they sometimes were in contact on a more casual level, such as answering questions over email, and they both said in unison that they "should" work more together.

The food waste expert had one answer to the question related to packaging:

A-FW: [...] the only thing I can see is that if we take meat, for example, where vacuum packaging is used, [...] I'm not an expert, but I understand that vacuum-packed meat lasts longer, and we can set longer shelf life dates and that every extra day of shelf life makes a huge difference for food waste. [...] The only thing I know is the question of vacuum-packed or not when it comes to meat; beyond that, I don't think I have much to add regarding packaging.

5.2.3 Case with smart packaging

The analysis question to the case was: what potentials and barriers does the retailer see in the smart packaging innovation. As the following section will enlighten, the retailers saw multiple barriers (see figure 12, and some potentials. The barriers were:

- Barrier 1: Legal limitation to not sell after use-by
- Barrier 2: Gaining the consumers trust for the innovation
- Barrier 3: Legal or medial ramifications if a consumer becomes ill after consumption
- Barrier 4: PPWR - The packaging might not be recyclable

Figure 12: A summary of the barriers found in the interpretation of the interview results.

The potentials they saw were:

- Potential 1: Reducing waste on the household level
- Potential 2: Interest in using it on a product with best before date
- Potential 3: Interest in using it on beef instead, larger economic incentive

Barriers

To start the discussion about the case packaging, the first question posed was an open-ended question about the experts' spontaneous reaction to the innovation. One of the packaging experts summarized the barriers for the packaging quite well in this first answer. The expert saw that the sensor was applied to a product with 'Use-by'-date, which are products that are not recommended to be consumed after the printed date. It is also forbidden by law to sell these products after the date has passed:

A-PAC: My spontaneous thought is that, under the current legislated system, it doesn't work. We have the [Use by-] date marking requirement that we must comply with. And we simply need to sell the product before it passes the date marking; otherwise, the product must be discarded. [...] It's not like you can say, 'Yes, it's still good, but we've passed the date—so we can sell it.' That's not how it works. Rather, if you sell it to the consumer before the date, and then the consumer could take responsibility for using it after the date has passed. That's the benefit you can get. But then the question is what trust the consumer has for this [product]. Also, will this packaging keep the chicken fresh longer than the date marking? How much do you gain from that?

The food waste expert at retailer A also summarized the barriers and added cost as an important gate keeper for the introduction of the packaging:

A-FW: First of all, the question is how much more expensive the product will become. That's number one. If it costs too much, it will never happen. No one will buy those products [to the stores] if they're too expensive. Number two, can we really trust it? If it's trustworthy, can we then ignore the best before date? Should it be removed altogether? What does the Food Agency say about that?

Together, these two quotes summarize quite well all the major barriers that was mentioned from all interviewed retailers. The largest barrier is that the innovation is put on a product with use-by-date. The second most important barrier was the price. This was mentioned by food waste experts and packaging experts alike. Even a small cost of 1 crown on the buyers price was could to be a too high barrier. Also, the relative cost of solving the chicken waste compared to the cost was mentioned.

C-PAC: You have to put this relation to everything else to consider. Like the price. How much does it cost? Is it expensive? Compared to the amount of waste with chicken that is? How big is the problem, and how much does it cost to solve it with this solution? [...] And how does this work in terms of recycling?

Another problem related to price was identified by A-FW, that is if the indicator would signal before the use-by-date:

A-FW: Then the question is, will it only alert us if it goes bad before the expiration date? Because you can't sell it after the use by-expiration date. So even if it's still good after that date,

we can't sell it. Then no one would want to take it in.

The combination of the fact that chicken cannot be sold after the use-by date and the risk that the sensor alert before the date, the incentives for the retailer seems small. There is quite substantial risk that the smart packaging application will only make their products more expensive. The packaging in itself will be more expensive, and if the sensors detect a spoilage before the last use by date, the retailer might have to waste the product. Simply – there is no economic win for the retailers right now.

One way to go around the barrier of use-by date is to sell before expiration and let the consumer make the decision to eat it after the date has passed. The retailers saw this as a better potential to reduce the food waste, rather than to use it with the intention to reduce the waste in store. But, for it to work in the consumer homes, the consumer need to trust it. Establishing this trust is therefore the second large barrier . One retailer answered that it has to work well even in a stressed situation.

A-PAC: [If we have a best before date, and an indicator like, this could It help reduce food waste?], To a small extent, in the home of the consumer. But then you really need to establish a trust in the indicator. The consumer needs to understand what it means, even in a stressful situation, when the kids are screaming. I think it's very difficult for the consumer to get there, considering the limited space for communication [on the packaging] and the quick decisions that have to be made. No, I'd say it's tricky

Some retailer believed that if this trust is gained by the consumer, the sensor might be able to fulfill its purpose. For gaining this trust communication was identified as central:

C-PAC: It's really about how it's communicated. If it's presented in a sensible way, it can definitely work. I believe people would trust something that measures thing, I really do. But it has to be communicated well.

Another view on how to gain trust, for both retail and consumer, was presented by B-FW, who said that if the innovation was safer than the current system with use-by-date it could have a potential to work:

B-FW: You would want to know in some way that this is a safer way to assess if the chicken is still good compared to the use-by date. [...] If that could be strengthened, it would be good.

But, even if the innovation would be trusted by consumers, there is a legal risk involved. That is, if the consumers buys a product at a retailer and becomes sick, who is the responsible part?

C-FW: I can imagine a scenario where a consumer buys a product from our store, and the use-by date has passed, but the [smart] label shows that it's okay. They eat it, get salmonella or something else, and then they call our company to complain. They might even sue us or whatever, and it could lead to a major shit storm. That risk exists for all retailers and brand owners, and I think that's a big reason why they might hesitate.

Beyond these already mentioned barriers, the packaging experts identified recyclable as an important gate keeper. As mentioned in the previous section of the interview results, recyclability was an important issue for the packaging experts, with the entry of PPWR. And complice to this is very important, as it will come to be a matter of extreme importance, as B-PAC summarizes it:

B-PAC: Unfortunately, with the introduction of PPWR and all the requirements that comes with it, the priority becomes complying with those requirements and adapting packaging accordingly,

rather than focusing on innovation such as smarter packaging. Because the consequences of not adhering to the legislation would be that we're not even allowed to put our products on the market at all.

So, from the packaging perspective, a non recyclable packaging is a deal breaker. And, as A-PAC mentioned in an earlier section, this regulation and demand does have a negative impact on food waste:

A-PAC:[...] And with this new legislation coming, it states that we should have recyclable packaging, but one can really wonder if they're thinking about food waste. Because it's not an equation that adds up right now. Maybe with technological development, but not at this moment.

Instead of this tray and cover plastic solution that the smart packaging currently uses, one of the Packaging experts mentioned another type of packaging:

A-PAC: For example, if you have a "flow pack" that is more like a pillow-packaging, you can reduce the material use. This makes it more similar to a mono-material and not as much laminate. With this type of packaging, you need a lot of laminate material. And the tray itself uses a lot of material compared to a more pillow-like packaging. [...]This one uses more material and more... 'messy' material, which can't be recycled, unlike a flow pack. Now, it might be the case that the customer doesn't want to buy chicken fillets in pillow packaging because they are not inclined to do so. It feels too messy. Plus, it's also very difficult to properly insert a chicken fillet into a flow pack. So, it might be a lost cause anyway.

Potentials

Some retailers said that the smart packaging might have a better potential for products with best before dates, since the current law allows products to be sold after this date has passed, whereas for use-by dates it is prohibited. At the time being, none of the retailer does actually do it (since the quality division wants to be careful about reclamations, according to A-FW). The retailer said that some meats might use best before rather than use by-dates, making them good candidate for the sensor. The retailer pointed out that this would be especially good because of the large climate impact of beef. Reducing waste for beef would in that sense have a bigger climate change impact.

A-FW: [...] should this really be on products with a use-by date? Isn't it better to have it on dairy products and other products that have a best-before date? Or... Beef? isn't it usually a use-by product, right? I think it has a best before date? [...] So it would make more sense to have such an indicator on those products, because you can sell them after the best before date. That would be more interesting, because then we could say that with an indicator like that, we could sell even after the best before date. But we can't do that with chicken.

For such a case, the food waste expert for retailer A had a more positive opinion about the innovation at it's chance to reduce food waste:

A-FW: Yes, when it comes to meat, if it means we can sell the product even after the best before date, then think, I'm even convinced, that we will reduce food waste. And I would say that it would especially help reduce food waste at home, because that's where people tend to throw things away the same day. So in households, it could really make a difference.

The A-FW expert was not the only expert to question if this innovation is best for chicken and if it actually could do a work to reduce food waste. C-PAC saw that the innovation might be more relevant for product

safety, rather than food waste:

C-PAC: This product [fresh chicken] has a use-by date. So it feels a bit like... I'm not sure how much food waste we might be saving with this. It seems like this product is more about protecting consumers than actually reducing food waste, now that I think about it. [...] It's more focused on product safety when you think about it. [...] Maybe it doesn't really serve the purpose then, actually. The idea itself is good, but I think the application for chicken might be the wrong fit.

6 Discussion

In this thesis, two research questions were posed. The first asked if it is possible to reach a scenario where a smart packaging can reduce the total environmental impact of a fresh chicken product, through reducing the amount of food waste. The second research question asked what potentials and barriers retailers see in a smart packaging innovation. In this section, the findings from the two parts will be discussed and summarized into a conclusion.

6.1 Discussing the LCA results

In the LCA study, the environmental impact of the sensor and chicken and packaging was evaluated for 15 impact categories. These results were used to calculate the possible improvement in the case scenarios, for different levels of waste reduction, owing to a successful use of the sensor. The results imply that it is theoretically possible to reach a lower environmental impact within some impact categories, such as climate change, water use, and eutrophication. But as table 8 shows, a reduction is not possible for all impact categories. For land use and two of the toxicology categories, the sensor adds impact which cannot be compensated by the level of decreased waste. Before further discussing the implications of the results, there is a need to discuss the accuracy and trustworthiness of the results themselves.

One of the most important aspects of performing an LCA study is the interpretation and the reflection on the results. The performed LCA study was highly explorative and unique, since no previous LCA studies on a smart packaging or a similar sensor was found in the literature. This means that the assumptions made in the calculations could not be related to another study, and thus validated through comparison. To evaluate the quality and reliability of the LCA results, other approaches must be made. In the LCA methodology described in ISO 14044 an important part of the interpretation is *completeness check, sensitivity check and consistency check*. In the scenario calculation, there are two parts that effect the results most: the sensor and the chicken data. The baseline packaging (tray and cover plastic) was included in both scenarios being compared, thereby canceling out its own impact in the two scenarios. The sensor and the chicken data are therefore particularly important to assess for quality and sensitivity, since they have the deciding affect on the case outcomes.

Sensitivity and completeness of sensor data

In the completeness check, the objective is to determine whether all necessary information and data required for interpretation are available and complete. In the calculations of the sensor's impact, no data on the energy consumption during the assembly process was included. The reason for this exclusion was lack of data and knowledge. The sensor is currently manufactured manually at a laboratory scale, and it was not possible to receive specific information about the lab's energy consumption, as multiple activities were carried out at the site, with sensor production representing only a minor fraction. Since no data could be presented, the assembly step was left out of the LCA calculation for the sensor. As a result, the current LCA results likely underestimate the sensor's impact to some extent. According to ISO 14044, when data is missing, it is essential to assess whether the absence of this information compromises the ability to meet the goal and scope of the LCA. In this case, the exclusion of assembly energy could lead to a non-conservative estimation of the results.

To evaluate the effects of underestimating the sensor's impact, a simple sensitivity analysis was conducted. It

is hard to predict how much impact the energy demand would add, and in the sensitivity analysis an increase 10% of in overall impact was investigated. When testing for an increased by 10% across all impact categories, the changes in the best-case scenario results were small. The only affected categories were Ecotoxicity, the two Human toxicity categories and Land Use, all which increased by 1 or 2% in comparison to the original result, see figure 9. Observe that these were the categories where the sensor added an impact that could not be compensated by the decrease in waste; the results in were positive as see in figure 8. These categories seem to be the most sensitive categories, which can be explained when looking at the distribution of impact between the three parts of the system in figure 7. In these four categories, the impact of the sensor is relatively large in comparison to the other parts, or at least closer to equally distributed between the three parts of the system. This means that increasing the impact by 10% as performed in the sensitivity analysis will alter the proportion between the parts more noticeably, than compared to the impact categories where the sensor has only a minor or negligible contribution to the overall impact. For these other categories, the sensor's impact is very small in comparison to chicken or packaging. Adding 10% impact in these other categories therefore had no effect on the overall case results.

The take away from this simple sensitivity analysis is that an increase by 10% of the sensor's LCA results did not drastically change the conclusions drawn from the case calculations. If 10% would correspond to the effects of adding the assembly process is hard to determine. Therefore, the missing the energy requirement decreases the trustworthiness to the results.

Sensitivity to the chicken data

The chicken dataset that was used might underestimate the climate impact of the chicken. Discussions with colleagues at RISE, along with an RISE-made report on Swedish chicken farming (Edman et al., 2022), indicated that the actual climate impact of Swedish chicken is estimated to be somewhat higher than what the dataset suggests. According to the report, the climate impact of chicken was estimated at 1.7 kg CO₂-equivalents per kilogram chicken delivered to retail gate, including packaging, whereas the dataset used in this study reported a lower value. The selected chicken data had a climate impact of 1.3 kg CO₂-equivalents per kilogram chicken, and the packaging had an impact around 0.1 kg CO₂-equivalents. Together, that is 0.3 kg lower than the RISE report finding. Although this is a relatively small difference, it underlines the importance of performing a sensitivity analysis.

In the sensitivity analysis for the chicken data, a 10% increase in climate impact corresponds to 1.43 kg CO₂-equivalents per kilogram of chicken. At this level of climate impact, the results from the case calculation remained unchanged, with an improvement of 12%. For the rest of the impact categories the effects are similar to the sensitivity analysis to the sensor- all categories were unaffected, except Ecotoxicity, the two human toxicity and Land use. For these four, the results were decreased by one percent. This could suggest that the calculated relative improvements from the case is relatively stable in 11 of the 15 categories, such as climate change and water use.

According to Rysselberge et al. (2021), the climate impact and overall environmental footprint of chicken can vary significantly depending on its origin. So, to test the robustness of the climate change impact category further, a sensitivity test for the climate category was performed. But even when the climate impact data was increased to 3 kg CO₂ per kilogram of chicken, to match the highest identified Swedish climate impact, the relative improvement remained at 12% reduction in the best-case scenario. Although it implies that the relative improvements might be robust for the climate change category, it has significant implications for the

absolute results. If a data set indicating a climate impact of 3 kg CO₂ per kilogram of chicken is used, the total improvement in absolute terms would be approximately 3.6 kg CO₂ per kilogram of chicken saved. In contrast, with the current dataset, the absolute improvement is more than half of that, at 1.3 kg CO₂ per kg chicken. Comparing to, for example, French chicken at 5 kg CO₂ per kilogram of chicken (Rysselberge et al., 2021), the results would differ even more. This highlights how much the choice of dataset for chicken influences the absolute outcomes of the LCA results.

This issue is a fundamental challenge in life cycle assessment (LCA): the results are highly dependent on the data. If the dataset is changed to either match the report from RISE (Edman et al., 2022), or to match international data, the conclusions in absolute terms differ. Choosing the appropriate data is therefore very important to get truthful results. However, it also raises the question of the importance of the absolute size of the LCA results. If the goal of the sensor is to decrease waste, it is not as important if waste is avoided for Swedish chicken or non-Swedish chicken; waste is still waste. But with the current formulation of research question one, which asks for the possible environmental improvements, this choice of chicken matters. If the winnings in environmental terms are deemed too small for the Swedish chicken, the argument could be to use the smart packaging for French chicken instead. Although theoretically true, it does not fully resonate with the goal of reducing food waste at a global level.

Implications from the LCA discussion

With the limitations and uncertainties in mind, a reasonable approach is to treat the LCA results with large uncertainty and to use them as indications rather than definite answers. For that reason, the results of the case were presented in a relative manner, where possible improvements were presented in whole-number percentages. When transforming these relative improvements to absolute numbers, the size is much dependent on the data that is used. A more general way to answer the first research question is to only use these relative improvements, and to use these results as an indication of the size of the possible improvement, not an exact value. In the best-case scenario, R+H, a decrease in environmental impact could be seen for ten of the impact categories. The size of the improvement varied between 9 and 12 percent. A generalization could be that a possible absolute best-case improvement could lie around 10 percent at most. So, in theory, it is possible to reach a decrease in environmental impact, but the extent of the reduction is limited, and it is not possible for all impact categories. For climate change, a ten percent reduced impact corresponds to around 0.13 kg saved CO₂ eq per kg of chicken product.

Note that it is only in the absolute best-case scenario, where chicken food waste is eliminated both at the retailer and in households, that this nearly 10% reduction in climate impact would be achieved. Such a best-case scenario might never be realistic. When the product is launched, it would probably require time for consumers to get to know the product and fully understand the sensor. It is not until trust and understanding have been established that the sensor can be used as intended. Cases of misunderstanding or misinterpretation will, of course, also exist, meaning that waste reduction in households might never reach a full 100% reduction. Considering cases where the sensor responds before the use-by date has passed, and the fact that the chicken product still can be forgotten in the back of the fridge, it seems rather impossible to reach a 100% decrease in chicken waste. A conservative suggestion, in line with the goal of food waste reduction stated by the Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2015), could be that a 50% waste reduction is perhaps more likely. For a 50% reduction in chicken waste in both households and retail, the environmental improvement could be around 5% for the possible impact categories. In climate change, this

corresponds to around 0.065 kg saved CO₂ eq per kg of chicken product.

Seeming as this is a rather small absolute improvement, it could be relevant to think about what food is used for this smart packaging innovation. Chicken has a rather low climate impact, but if a product of higher environmental impact, such as meat is used in this packaging, the saved in environmental impact for each non-wasted product is much higher. If the goal is to decrease the environmental impact as much as possible, this should be considered. Beef, for example, has a much higher climate impact than chicken. The chicken used in the LCA study has a climate impact of 1.3 kg CO₂ per kg chicken, and minced beef of Swedish origin had has a climate impact of 19.5 kg CO₂ per kg beef, according to data from the RISE food database. Every saved unit of beef would therefore save around 15 times more climate impact compared to chicken.

According to research question one, the goal was to determine if it is possible to reach a situation where the total environmental impact of a smart packaging chicken product is decreased by reduced waste level. The answer to this research question is partly yes; it is theoretically possible to reach a scenario where the environmental impact in some categories, such as climate change, water use and eutrophication, is reduced as a consequence of reduced waste. But as table 8 shows, a reduction is not possible for all impact categories. For land use and two of the toxicology categories, the sensor adds an impact which cannot be compensated by the level of decreased waste that was researched. But these results, and the absolute size of the improvement are highly dependent on the data that is used, and the product that is packed. If the goal is to maximize the environmental gain, a product with higher environmental impact than chicken could be considered, such as beef.

6.2 Discussing the Interviews

The first and most imperative finding from the interviews is that this innovation is not well suited for the current legal system. For food safety requisites, the fresh type of chicken product which the biosensor is applied on has a use-by date, and it is not permitted to sell a product after this date. This means that retailers will not be able to use the sensor to decrease their waste level; to the opposite, it might only increase their waste. There could be cases where the sensor signals that the product has spoiled before the date has passed, something that is not possible to detect with an ordinary packaging without a sensor. The only way for the sensor to fulfill its purpose for this type of use-by product is if a consumer buys it before the date has passed and they themselves decide to consume it. But for this case, there could be legal and medial ramifications if the consumer gets sick after consumption, ramification due to which some retailers might be hesitant to try the innovation on their products, as one of the interviewees pointed out. Even if the retailers themselves are not legally responsible, be it the producer of the chicken or the producer of the sensor, such events could attract medial attention were the retailer comes into a bad light. Both this risk of bad-will, in the rare cases of illness, and the fact that the product cannot be sold after use-by date, drastically decrease the possibility for the sensor-packaging to reach the retailers, and by that the market itself. This decreases the innovation's realistic potential to decrease chicken food waste substantially.

Connecting this to the possible best case scenario presented in the discussion of the LCA results, it is a strong argument against that a 100% reduction at both retailer and households could be reached for this type of product. A change of date marking, from use-by to best-before would be necessary in order to unlock the potential to reduce the waste at the retailers, either by a change in regulations or by applying the innovation to a product which has a best-before date.

Beyond the legal hinder, the cost was also considered very important. One interviewee claimed that no retailer would take in this type of sensor-product if it was more expensive for the retailers, in comparison to other products. Several retailers expressed how thoroughly their buyers calculate the margins of each product. Although expressed as a barrier, arguing with cost could be a potential way in for the product. Being able to argue that this innovation could reduce the waste, and thus increase the fraction of sold products, might be a way to bring the sensor to the retailers interest. But this of course requires that the product has a best-before date, otherwise no such advantage can be made. Although this is a rather monumental hinder the retailers saw some potentials and actually expressed interest in using it for products with the best before date, such as meat where the cost of waste is high, due to the high price of meat.

Another large challenge to introduce this smart packaging innovation is that the packaging experts are already highly occupied with something else - the new EU regulation on packaging and packaging waste (PPWR). Two of the interviewed experts expressed how much of their work revolved around following this regulation, and how hard it was to manage everything with the time limits of the business mutual plastic goals, set to 2025 for recyclability, and 2030 for renewable materials. One of the retailers admitted that they would fail this timeline, another expressed that they had extended it. With endorsing recyclability being the most urgent question on the minds of the packaging experts, introducing an innovation which could lead to less recyclability of the packaging is not a sound idea. One of packaging experts did a quick evaluation of the smart sensor label, and said that the large label on the cover plastic, containing the sensor, could be a problem for recyclability. Labels are in general a problem for recyclability, and since the sensor-label is a bit thicker than ordinary labels, it could be a problem.

While the packaging experts are having a hard time reaching their goals within PPWR, the food waste experts are making good pace towards their food waste goal. All retailers had entered into business mutual goal to have their food waste to 2025, in comparison to the baseline year 2016. For most, this meant reaching a level below 1% waste. Reaching this seemed possible according to the interviewed experts. Two of the three retailers expressed detailed strategies, much focused on data collection and system understanding. By working preventative, and by reducing the price on products close to expiry, they were steadily improving. Especially reducing the price close to expiry was expressed a key enablers. The waste levels for fresh chicken was already low, and none of the retailer saw this as an area of special challenge. One mentioned that products with short expiry date, such as chicken can be problematic, especially since there are a lot of campaigns within this section. Campaigns could, expressed another experts, complicate the auto-ordering for the non-campaign chicken, leading to over-ordering if it was not adjusted for.

All in all, the experts did not believe they had an unmanageable problem within the fresh chicken category. Although a slight window of opportunity can be seen within the short date-products as expressed by one retailer, this problem can be managed by other means as well. This implies that the the sensor does not solve as much of a problem which cannot be targeted with other methods. As expressed, there is waste due to short date on fresh chicken, but since the products cannot be sold after expiry-date, the sensor could not "save" the retailers in this situation, as one of the interviewees expressed it. In order to target this group, there has to be a change in regulation, which is hard to predict if there would be.

To conclude the discussion of the results found in the interviews, and to answer the second research question: The retailers identified multiple barriers, some which are hard to go around unless the innovation is placed on another product, and other which might be overcome with communication, but communication is one of the hardest thing there is, as one of the experts expressed. The barriers can be summarized into technical

and social barriers, as presented in figure 12. The technical barriers are: use-by date for chicken products, the question of recyclability, and the cost for retailers as well as consumers. The social barriers are: trust, even in stressful situations; understanding, interpretation the sensor correctly; and lastly the risk for medial ramification in cases of illness.

6.3 Combining the LCA and the interviews

Combining the discussions concerning the LCA analysis and the interview results, we started out with a theoretical potential of decreasing the environmental impact for some categories, including climate change and water use, with around 10% in the absolute best-case scenario where the current waste level is compared to a 100% reduction, i.e an abolishment, of waste in both household and in the retailers. In the LCA discussion, it was acknowledged that this 100% reduction is theoretically unprobable, due to possible cases of misunderstanding or misuse by consumers, and early detection of spoilage at the retailers. In the interview discussion the sensor's potential was further undermined, by facts such as the inability for retailers to sell fresh chicken products after use-by date. The potential thus decreases drastically, and reaching 100% food waste decrease is not realistic. Instead, a 50% reduction, according to the UN goal, 'for 2030, was mentioned as a benchmark.

This suggestion of lower success-rate of the sensor underlines that, if the goal is to reduce the environmental impact of the eaten food, an alternative could be to apply the sensor for a product with higher environmental impact. Seeing as there are already arguments against chicken both because of use by date and the relative low climate impact it might be a better idea to use it for another product which has a higher climate impact. In that way, the food waste reduction saves more food with a higher environmental burden from being waste.

One potential product group which can have best-before date was suggested by the interviewed retailers - beef products. Beef was believed to in some cases be marked with a best-before date rather than use-by. This is correct, since for beef products, and most other products, it is up to the producer to decide if the product should be marked with best-before or use-by (Livsmedelsverket, 2024). The only product group which has a regulatory demand for use-by marking is actually fresh poultry, according to Livsmedelsverket (2024). The choice to apply this sensor to a chicken product is therefore unfortunate, in this perspective. For all other products, where the producer themselves decide which of the expiration dates to apply, it could be easier to introduce the sensor, and make retailers interested in using them, since best-before allows the product to be sold after the date has passed. Two of the food waste experts also pointed out that the amount of waste, measured in lost income, is largest within the meat category. Since meat is a very expensive product, even a low waste fraction gives a large economic impact. Perhaps the sensor could be introduced to the market on such products, as ground beef, where the advantages are in plural both in the name of sustainability and for the retailers, who have a chance to save more money for every product which is sold instead of wasted. And later, as both consumers and retailers are familiarized with the sensor it could be introduced to more sensitive food such as fresh chicken.

Using the sensor for a beef product would go around the hindrance of not getting to sell after used-by date, and as pointed out by the retailers in the interviews, it also has a stronger sustainability incentive. As stated earlier, beef has about a 15 times higher climate impact in comparison to chicken. Every saved unit of beef would therefore save around 15 times more climate impact compared to chicken. So, for meat there is both an environmental and economical incentive for retailers to use the product.

Continuing on the thought of applying the sensor to beef products, a possibility which intertwines the packaging problem with the food waste question arises. Some meat products have of lately been packed in so called flow-packs, mentioned by one of the interviewees. These pillow-like packages require less material, and can be made of mono-plastics, making them a good alternative according to the PPWR-rules. If the sensor could be applied to a flow pack, this could be a way to get the packaging experts on board. In this study, the base-line packaging was assumed to be a plastic tray with cover plastic. This packaging has an modified atmosphere (MAP), where gas is injected to prevent or slow down spoilage. This atmosphere is necessary for the sensors function, since it reacts to gases in the atmosphere. The flow-pack, is according to one of the interviewees, also a MAP, which theoretically could make it possible to add the sensor. Further research should therefore investigate the potential to use the sensor in this type of packaging.

6.4 Concluding: What is the potential of smart packaging innovations?

So, can smart packaging help us decrease food waste? Through the LCA study, in combination with the interviews, we have learned that the sensor might have a possibility to reduce the climate impact, as well as some other environmental impact categories. But this reduction is dependent on the success of the sensor, that is, that it actually convince retailers and consumer to not waste the product if it is still good. The question of food waste is therefore much a question of behavior and culture, both which may change over time with learning.

The central idea with the sensor is to motivate the consumers to question the absoluteness of the date marking. If this is successful, could learning from the sensor that the packed product still is good inspire learning for other products? Could the sensor inspire an even broader behavior change than just for the product it is applied to?

Researchers, as well as the interviewees in this thesis, have commented on the consumers strong belief in the date mark system (Wikström, Williams, 2023). They have noted that consumers throw away food without thinking twice if it could still be good. It is from these types of observation that smart packaging such as the examined biosensor has been developed. If the sensor successfully makes consumers change behavior around the product it is applied to, could it perhaps inspire consumers to question the date marking and on other products as well? If this type of learning could be inspired, the potential of the biosensor to reduce waste would extend beyond the product it is applied to. That would be a dream come true, but is it probable?

Wikström, Williams (2023) express that one need the consumer have in order to affect their food waste is knowledge about if food is still good, and this sensor could provide that. In a study concerning consumer acceptance of smart packaging including nanotechnology, Henschion et al. (2019) found that the technology has a better chance to gain acceptance if consumer perspective is introduced early in the development process, and if it brings about advantages that the consumer actually is interested in, such as improved food safety or low price. Another Irish study on consumer awareness for smart technology concluded that there is a potential for these types of innovations, provided that the consumers are sufficiently educated or made aware of them (Callaghan et al., 2016). The authors pointed out that consumers need to be made aware that smart packaging already exists, and that it therefore is not as foreign as it might seem. Seeming as the sensor fulfills a need that the consumer has(Wikström, Williams, 2023), the requirement Henschion et al. (2019) expressed is met. This suggest that the sensor could have a potential to help consumers decrease their waste. But as Callaghan et al. (2016) noted, the question of communication is important to reach success. Making the consumers understand the sensor, and building the foundations of trust is paramount for the success of the

technology. Together these three studies point toward a possible success with gaining the consumers trust and achieve the sought after behavioral change to reduce food waste.

On the other hand, there is a need to acknowledge that the sensor could have the opposite learning outcome. In a case were the consumers learn to trust the sensor, there could be a risk that a dependence on the technology to make judges about food quality and food safety is developed or endorsed. By getting used to having the information of freshness from the sensor, the consumers could develop an even stronger sense of uncertainty towards food without such an indicator. That is, that consumers are even more strict to follow the date mark labeling for those products. Instead of inspiring learning, the sensor encourages skepticism and technology-dependence. The trust that consumers were expressed to have in the date making, such stated by the interviewees, might be moved to the sensor technology. This is of course a worst case speculation, but it should be mentioned as a possible effect when discussing the potentials of introducing smart technology to decrease food waste.

A probable scenario, once the technology is introduced, is that some consumers develop trust and change their behavior for both the applied product and for some other products, while others might remain reserved and only trust products past expiry with a sensor, and some might not trust the sensor at all. The important question is then which of the three behaviors get the most followers.

To make better predictions of consumer behaviors, there is a need for insight by further research. A consumer study could clear this out. In the beginning of this project, it was my ambition to include interviews with consumers as well, to investigate this question. With the limitation and with regards to the time consumption of both performing and analyzing interviews, the research was limited to only the interviews with the retailers. This proved to be a sound decision, as no in-depth interviews with retailers on this matter is previously published. As stated int the introduction, there is already numerous studies which investigates consumer behavior, as well a couple concerning consumer attitudes towards smart packaging. By looking to these studies, a speculative discussion on potential consumer behaviors can be made, as has been used in above.

One last remark: Although I have expressed that saving food from being waste would decrease the climate impact, this is a false description. No matter if the food is eaten or if it is thrown away, it as already been produced and the environmental impact has already occurred. The only way for food to reduce impact, is by producing less. Decreasing food waste is thus a long-term project. The climate impact that we "save" by eating all our food is only reached when that lead to less food being produced. Today around a third of the food we produced is wasted, at different stages in the food chain and for different reasons. One could way that in relation to what we eat, we *overproduce* 30% food, which generated an extra 30% environmental impact, land use, water use, etc. Still, there is famine in some parts of the world. In others, obesity is a problem. Food waste is thus a question of equality and social sustainability, as much as it is a question of environmental sustainability for our planet and economic sustainability for both the household and the common economy. Solving the packed problem for fresh meats is only a small step toward sustainability, but it is these small steps that one day could lead to a whole sustainable journey.

7 Conclusions

The aim of this thesis was to explore the potential of smart packaging to reduce food waste and, by doing so, decrease the total environmental impact of consumed food.

The results indicate that the environmental impact can be reduced but that the extent of reduction is limited, and does not include all impact categories. The absolute size of the improvements highly depend on the data that is used. By acknowledging the uncertainties in the LCA method and with a rough estimate based on the LCA results, a 50% reduction in food waste, in line with the goals expressed by the UN sustainable development goal 12.3, could perhaps lead to a reduced impact of around 5% compared to today's waste levels. For climate impact, this reduction would save approximately 0.065 kg of CO₂ per kg of chicken product.

Through the interviews with food waste and packaging experts in the retailing sector, important barriers to the introduction and success of the sensor were identified. The barriers were summarized into technical and social barriers. The technical barriers included: the requirement of use-by dates for fresh chicken products, which means a prohibition to sell the product after the expiration date has passed; the question of whether the packaging is fully recyclability; and the increased cost for this type of smart packaging product. The social barriers were: trust for the technology, even in stressful situations; understanding and interpreting the sensor correctly; and lastly, the risk of media ramifications for the retailers in cases of illness. The largest barrier was the law requiring that fresh chicken products must have a use-by date labeling. This makes selling the product after its expiration date impossible, even with a sensor indicating that it is still good.

Of these barriers, a solution that avoids at least three of them was suggested: using the smart sensor for a beef product instead of chicken. For beef, the environmental impact per kilogram is 15 times larger than the impact of chicken, meaning that reducing food waste for these products has a larger absolute impact. The second advantage of using beef is that the products can be sold with a use-by date label, enabling sales after the expiration date. The third advantage is that retailers have a larger economic loss for beef in comparison to chicken. Reducing waste for beef, therefore, has a larger economic incentive for the retailers. Beef can also be packed in a fully recyclable packaging, so-called flow-pack. Applying the sensor to this type of product could be examined in further studies as a way to introduce the smart packaging solution to the market.

To summarize the findings, there exists potential for smart packaging technology such as this gas sensor. The next question to examine, in order to utilize this potential, is gaining the trust of the consumers. Further research should therefore focus on consumer perception of the smart packaging innovation and if it could be the solution to the packed problem.

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Appendix - Interview guide

The following interview guide was used in the interviews with the retailers. Since the interviews were performed in Swedish, the interview guide is written in Swedish.

0 INFORMATION OM INTERVJUN

Hej! Kul att höras

- Hur mår du idag?
- Jag mår bra,
- Innan vi kör igång tänkte jag dra lite information och presentera mitt projekt och mig själv. Sen bollar jag över frågor till dig. Låter det bra?

Välkommen till intervjun. Jag tänker att jag börjar med att **presentera mig själv** lite mer.

- Jag heter Lydia och studerar mitt sista år på civilingenjörsprogrammet i **ekosystemteknik** vid LTH. Utbildningen handlar i stort om att **förstå miljöproblem som svävar på planet mellan teknik och samhälle**.
- De här intervjuerna är en del av mitt **examensarbete**. Arbetet genomförs under en termin och jag är ungefär halvvägs nu. Min forskningsfråga handlar ju om matsvinn, och **hur förpackningsinnovation kan hjälpa oss att minska** både mängden svinn och den totala miljöpåverkan. Det undersöker jag dels genom en LCA-modellering på den specifika **förpackningsinnovationen** i kycklingförpackning som jag ska berätta mer om på slutet, både för base line scenario och **om man kan lyckas minska** svinn. Detaljerna om förpackningen kommer jag berätta mot slutet av intervjun, så för nu blir det lite av en **cliffhanger**. LCA-modellen kommer jag att komplettera med dessa intervjuer, där jag ställer frågor om hur handlare arbetar med svinn och om innovation kan ha potential till minskat svinn i butik och hem.
 - Några frågor om mitt projekt innan jag går vidare på information om intervjun?
- Jag genomför det här arbetet som i tre roller kan man säga
 - Fristående forskare (LTH)
 - Konsult på RISE och deras intressen i micoorch
 - Men jag är också en självständig individ

Om intervjun – hur datan kommer användas:

- Okej att spela in?
- Du, företag anonym i data och rapport
- Ämnar inte att jämföra andra utpekande sätt

Samtycke:

Samtycker du att jag använder informationen från den här intervjun till att:

- Underlag till min LCA-modellering
- Underlag till min diskussion, där citat kan komma att användas
 - Citat och uttalanden ska inte användas för att peka ut enskilda handlare, utan för att resonera om problemet
- Del informationen med RISE, LTH och andra intressenter inom forskningsvärlden
- Det vi pratar om på **intervjun** idag kommer jag att **använda** både som **data** till en LCA-modell på förpackningen och som **underlag** till min **diskussion**.
- Du och ditt företag kommer att vara helt anonym. Jag kommer att intervjua alla stora handlare i Sverige, s och era svar kommer inte att jämföras och utvärderas mot varandra på ett utpekande sett. I och med att alla ställt upp blir det dessutom mer anonymt. och jag ämnar inte peka ut svar från specifika handlare jämföra sinsemellan.
 - Låter det bra? Har du frågor om det?
- Arbetet beräknas vara klart i slutet på oktober. Jag skickar gärna resultaten till er.

Etik:

- Alltid rätt att avbryta
- Inte uppge anledning
- Möjligt att dra tillbaka ditt samtycke, maila mig.
- Intervjun semistrukturerad
 - Frågor, inte kritiskt hålla oss till
 - Se som normalt samtal
 - Jag kanske styr oss tillbaka
 - Ok "inte veta" / Behöva tänka
 - Låter bra?

1 STRATEGI OCH INTRODUKTION

- Om dig
 - o Berätta kort om din roll och vad den innehåller
 - o Hur länge arbetat detta uppdrag (tidigare roller? Din motivation
 - o Kan du berätta lite kor om er företagsstruktur?

- Vill du berätta om er **matsvinnstrategi** på ert företag?
- **Hemsidan** Läst ni ska ha halverat matsvinn
 - o Jämfört med vilket basår? Hur går det?
 - o Vad innebär ert **mål för handlingar**?
 - o viktiga prioriteringar / Faktiska handlingar /Interna mål / Externa mål

- Vad är största anledningen till **att ni arbetar** för att minska er matsvinn?
 - o (Ekonomiskt / hållbarhet / annat)
 - o Vilka fler anledningar finns det än den viktigaste

- Vad är **anledningarna** till att det uppstår matsvinn?
 - o Datum (hur ofta, i %) / Bruten förpackning / Fel / dålig
 - o Annat?

- Typer av **svinnminskning**: Enligt hemsidan
 - o Förädla, Donnera, appar, nedsättning
 - o Vilken gör ni mest av?

- En del av er strategi är ju **nedsatt pris**
 - o Hur? När och till vilken nivå sker nedsättning. **Planerbarhet?**
 - o Ungefär **hur många procent** av varor säljer ni **nedsatt** i svinnsmart?
 - o Finns det någon kategori av varor som **dominerar** här?

- Vad skulle du säga är **ert störst problem** just nu relaterat till matsvinn?
 - o Vad är det **viktigaste problemet att lösa**, kopplat till matsvinn enligt dig?
 - o Finns det något annat som skapar **frustration** för dig?

- Vad händer med **den mat ni inte kan sälja**?
 - o Hanterar ni maten på andra sätt än svinnsmart
 - o Eget kök / Matavfall / energiåtervinning / Vålgörenhet / TGTG / annat?
 - o Har ni övervägt att hitta en avsättning eller sälja det som kan göra det till annan produkt (B2B)?

- Utbildning

Appendix - Interview guide

- Vilken typ av utbildning får de i er organisation? Olika beroende på var?

Reservfrågor

- **Inköpsplanering** nämns ofta som något viktigt
 - Hur går inköp till hos er?
 - Handlaren själv? / Centralt planerat? / automatiskt system?
- Använder ni er av **mängdrabatter**?
 - Hur tror du att det påverkar svinnet hemma?
- (Vad består din **dag-till-dag** av som matsvinnsexpert?)

2 SVINN I SIFFROR

Nu kommer jag att ställa mer detaljerade frågor om det svinn som uppstår i er koncern

- Vilken **kategori** av varor har ni **mest** svinn i. Mest **Värde** i
 - Har du statistik på alla kategorier
 - Hur används svinnstatistiken i ert företag? / Ditt arbete
 - Hur vanligt är det att maten slängs på grund av att datumet har passerat
- Hur **mycket svinn** är det i kött
 - % / kg / kr
 - Har du möjlighet att dela **data** med mig till **LCA**?
- Hur mycket för färsk **kyckling**, skiljer det sig?
 - Vad är anledningarna
 - Hur ser svinnrutinerna ut?
- Hur vanligt är det att maten slängs på grund av att datumet har passerat
 - **Prisnedsätts köttprodukter** hos er?

3 DATUMSYSTEMT

Nu kommer jag att ställa lite frågor om datumsystemet som för nuvarande används för att märka varor. Datumsystemet består ju av både bäst före och sista förbrukningsdag.

- **Vad tycker du**, som matsvinnsexpert, om **datumsystemet**
 - Fungerar det? Uppfyller det sitt syfte?
 - Finns det några **problem** med det?
- Använder ni **systemet i era rutiner**, ex när varor prisnedsätts eller inventeras?

Appendix - Interview guide

- Säljer ni varor till nedsatt pris då de har kort datum?
- Finns det **bättre** sätt **än datumsystem**?
 - o Tror du att dammsystemet är **här för att hålla**, eller finns det bättre metoder?
 - o Finns det andra sätt att arbeta än det som ni redan gör idag?

4 OM FÖRPACKNINGAR

Nu ska vi prata mer om matförpackningens roll i det hela. I mitt arbete är det just skärningspunkten mellan matsvinn och förpackning. Innan jag går in mer på det skulle jag vilja höra om dina tankar:

- Vilka **kopplingar** ser du (i din roll) mellan förpackningen och matsvinn.
 - o I butik
 - o I hemmen
- Ser du **konfliktytor**?
- är det här något ni tänker på i er **matsvinn-strategi**? Eller omvänt
 - o **Arbetar du tillsammans** med förpack?
- Om nej: Va är viktigt för i ert **förpackningstänk**
 - o Vilka **prioriteringar** har ni när ni väljer förpackningar till era varor
 - o Är dessa prioriteringar viktigt när ni väljer att köpa in **annan mat**?
 - o Kan du berätta om någon specifik **produkt**?
- **Förpackningen** i sig har ju också en **miljöpåverkan**?
 - o Inverkar det på de beslut ni gör i **designprocessen**?
 - o Är det viktigt att den alltid är låg?

5 CASET: SMARTA FÖRPACKNINGAR

- a. Smarta sensorer – känner till?
 - i. Potential smarta sensorer?
- b. **Caset 0**: beskriv allmänt om caset
 - i. Spontant + frågor?
 - ii. Fördelar / Nackdelar? Potential att minska svinn? Planerbarhet?
- c. **Case 1-3**: Visa de olika bilderna
- d. Tror du att **denna fungerar för att minska svinn**?

Appendix - Interview guide

- i. I matbutik / I hushåll
 - ii. Fungerar denna med er strategi kring matsvinn?
 - iii. Ser du risker för **ökat svinn**?
- e. Om datum
- i. **Datum vs sensor**, vilka fördelar finns det? Nackdelar?
 - ii. Tror du att sensor kan **ersätta datum (hypotetisk framtid)**
- f. Om Kostnad av sensor-produkt
- i. Hur stort tror du kostnadshindret är för att denna ska lyckas?
 - ii. För konsument, intresse att köpa:
 1. Lite dyrare, 10k
 2. Samma pris
 3. Billigare
- g. För er. Om ni tror på varan, vad är ni villiga att betala för den?
- i. Mer? Samma? Mindre?
 - ii. Hur brukar det se ut vid lanseringar?
- h. Hinder - Vad skulle krävas för att ni ska ta in den:
1. Mer fakta
 2. Konsumentundersökning acceptans
 3. Konsumentundersökning pris
 4. Vetenskaplig redogörelse att och hur den funkar

1. Sammanfattning - Frågor om Sensorn:

- a. Vad ser ni för fördelar?
- b. Vad ser ni för nackdelar?
- c. Tror ni att denna har potential att minska matsvinn
- d. Hur stort tror du kostnadshindret är för att denna ska lyckas?
- e. Hinder - Vad skulle krävas för att ni ska ta in den:
- f. Tror du att sensor kan **ersätta datum (hypotetisk framtid)**
- g. Tror ni att sensorer och denna typ av innovation är en viktig del av framtidens matkedja?
- h. Övriga kommentarer?